

A sensitivity analysis of electron injection and acceleration in LWFA using PIConGPU

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Abstract

Laser-plasma accelerators (LPAs) hold great promise for generating high-charge, low-emittance electron beams with various applications in science and industry. However, their integration into high-demand applications requires precise control of the properties of the generated electron beams, which is not yet fully achieved and requires further understanding of the underlying dynamics. Three-dimensional particle-in-cell (PIC) simulations are the leading method to model relativistic laser-plasma interactions and probing the dynamics of these LPAs.

In this study, a realistic experimental setup of a laser wakefield accelerator (LWFA) employing self-truncated ionization injection was recreated using the open-source PIC code PIConGPU. Translating experimental conditions into simulations is inherently difficult due to the large number of possibly unknown laser and plasma parameters and their fluctuation in the experiment. To address this challenge, a Bayesian optimization campaign was conducted, employing an iterative feedback loop to explore the parameter space efficiently. This optimization framework was implemented with Snakemake, a Python-based workflow engine that automated and simplified the submission process of the simulations.

The recreated experimental setup enabled not only a better understanding of the experiment, but also a detailed multi-dimensional mapping of laser and plasma parameters to electron beam properties. This study offers a comprehensive, highly detailed analysis of LWFA electron beam characteristics, uncovering complex multi-parameter dependencies. The findings provide valuable guidance for experimentalists, enabling optimized input parameters and improved efficiency in achieving high-quality electron beams.

Zusammenfassung

Laser-Plasma-Beschleuniger (LPA) sind eine vielversprechende Methode für die Erzeugung von Elektronenstrahlen mit hoher Ladung und geringer Divergenz für Anwendungen in Wissenschaft und Industrie. Ihre Integration in anspruchsvolle Anwendungen erfordert jedoch eine präzise Kontrolle der Elektronenstrahleigenschaften, die noch nicht vollständig erreicht ist und ein tieferes Verständnis der zugrunde liegenden Dynamik voraussetzt. Dreidimensionale Particle-in-Cell (PIC) Simulationen sind die führende Methode zur Modellierung relativistischer Laser-Plasma Wechselwirkungen und zur Untersuchung der Dynamik von LPA.

In dieser Arbeit wurde ein realistischer experimenteller Aufbau eines Laser-Wakefield-Beschleunigers (LWFA), der mit selbsttrunkierter Ionisationsinjektion betrieben wird, mit Hilfe des Open-Source-PIC-Codes PIConGPU nachgebildet. Die Nachbildung der experimentellen Bedingungen in Simulationen ist aufgrund der großen Anzahl potentiell unbekannter Laser- und Plasmaparameter und deren Fluktuation während des Experiments anspruchsvoll. Um das zu bewältigen, wurde eine Bayes'sche Optimierung durchgeführt, die den Parameterraum iterativ und effizient absampelt. Diese Optimierung wurde mit Snakemake durchgeführt, einer Python-basierten Workflow-Engine, die die Durchführung der Simulationen automatisiert und vereinfacht.

Der nachgestellte Versuchsaufbau ermöglichte nicht nur ein besseres Verständnis des Experiments, sondern auch eine detaillierte mehrdimensionale Zuordnung der Laser- und Plasmaparameter zu den Eigenschaften des Elektronenstrahls. Diese Studie liefert eine umfassende und detaillierte Analyse der Eigenschaften des Elektronenstrahls und zeigt komplexe Abhängigkeiten von multiplen Parametern auf. Die Ergebnisse liefern wertvolle Hinweise zur Optimierung der Eingangsparameter und zur Steigerung der Effizienz bei der Erzeugung qualitativ hochwertiger Elektronenstrahlen im Experiment.

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1 Introduction

Accelerating particles has been a cornerstone of scientific and technological progress for decades. From cutting-edge research to medical applications and even household technologies, fast particles play an essential role. For instance, the cathode-ray tube (CRT) televisions of the past—although large by modern standards—are effectively small particle accelerators. However, when compared to colossal facilities like the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN [1], with its 27-kilometer circumference and network of pre-accelerators, CRTs are indeed "tiny."

Modern particle accelerators are monumental endeavors, often requiring multi-million or even billion-dollar investments. Their size and complexity continue to grow to achieve the ever-increasing particle energies and qualities demanded by contemporary research. While heavy charged particles can benefit from cyclic accelerators that reuse the same accelerating structures multiple times, light charged particles such as electrons suffer significant energy losses due to synchrotron radiation when their trajectories are bent at relativistic energies. This necessitates the construction of increasingly lengthy linear accelerators, posing both technical and economic challenges [2].

To address these limitations, advanced and innovative accelerator concepts are being explored to break this trend. Among the most promising approaches is the concept of the laser plasma accelerator (LPA), first introduced by Tajima and Dawson in 1979 [3]. LPAs use short intense laser pulses, which are directed to a plasma target and excite a plasma wave. Comparable to how a boat passing through water creating a wake behind it. The electrons can "surf" on this wake and gain energy on the way. This concept allows for much smaller accelerators since it reaches accelerating gradients in order of 100 GV m^{-1} [4]. With this technique, it was possible to reach electron bunches with a few nC charge and energies of more than 100 MeV, but the quality of the beams remained poor during the early decades of LPA development. The energy distribution was continuous from a few MeV to the highest energies, while most electrons only reached energies below 10 MeV [5, 6]. It took until 2004 to improve the control over the beam properties to achieve strong enough laser intensities to reach the newly discovered blowout regime [7, 8, 9, 10]. Since then enhancing the quality of the beam properties further is an ongoing challenge.

Good beam properties such as small energy spread and a small divergence are required for many applications. Recently, a free-electron laser (FEL) with laser-accelerated electrons was operated at the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf e. V. (HZDR) [11]. There the accelerated electrons are guided into an undulator where they are exposed to alternating magnetic fields and begin to "wiggle". This oscillation movement can cause coherent radiation to be emitted in the X-ray range if set up correctly. To make this work, low divergence electron beams with high charge and low energy spread are required.

To reach the required beam properties to operate an FEL, fundamental knowledge about

the acceleration process is required. Since the actual interaction takes place on a very short time and length scale, observing the dynamics of the laser plasma interaction in experiments is difficult. Purely theoretical calculations also struggle to model the complexity. To still gain an understanding, it became common to use particle-in-cell (PIC) simulations to model the interaction [12, 13]. These simulations allow the interactions to be observed in detail and provide information about the physical properties of the electron beam and the plasma wake at any point in time. These detailed insights can help to better understand the acceleration process and consequently to better control the electron beam parameters and to improve the stability for the operating an FEL.

The goal of this work is to support the continuous improvement of electron beam parameters with realistic simulations. Therefore, this work aims to create a multidimensional mapping of different laser and plasma parameters to electron properties and uncover more information about the physical processes that drive these dependencies.

To achieve this, an overview of the physics required to model an LPA experiment is given in chapter 2. Then, a brief introduction to PIC simulations is given, and the implementation of a workflow manager to automate the execution of the many simulations required for the following investigations is presented in chapter 3. With the option of automated simulation execution, chapter 4 explores a simulation setup to reproduce an experimental campaign. This setup is investigated in chapter 5 with respect to the dependence of the electron bunch properties on the laser and plasma configuration. Finally, a conclusion and outlook are given in chapter 6.

2 Introduction to Laser Wakefield Accelerators

2.1 From conventional accelerators to laser plasma accelerators

Accelerated electrons have applications in research, medicine, industry and many more fields. Electrons are charged particles and can be accelerated by an electric field. The simplest way to accelerate electrons is to expose them to a static electric field. The electric field is created through applied voltage between an anode and a cathode. In electrostatic accelerators, the reached energy is given by the product of the charge of the particle and the voltage difference between the cathode and the anode. The reachable energy is limited to a few tens of MeV, due to electric breakdown at higher voltages [14].

To exceed these energies, a successful idea was to propagate the charged particle through multiple accelerating stages, where each stage acts as an electrostatic accelerator. Such accelerators are a form of linear accelerators or short linacs. The accelerating stages are usually called cavities, inside which an accelerating field is present. As the electron passes through the first cavity, it is accelerated and enters the second cavity. When the electron is between the cavities, the signs of the electric fields change. This is achieved by an oscillator that controls the voltage of the cavities.

The frequency at which the sign of the field changes is called the radio frequency RF. It is important to match the RF and the length of the cavity to the speed of the particle beam so that the particles experience an accelerating field in each cavity. Since the particles are accelerated when going through the accelerator, either the RF or the length of each cavity needs to increase in order to fulfill this requirement. The average accelerating field, which can be produced by a linear accelerator is between 15 MV m^{-1} and 75 MV m^{-1} [15]. Therefore, they require a length of approximately 2 m to 7 m to accelerate electrons to more than 100 MeV.

To reduce the size of the accelerator or to create even higher energies, it is possible to build circular accelerators. But circular accelerators are not very efficient for accelerating light charged particles, since they lose a lot of energy due to radiation losses. For heavier charged particles, like ions, circular accelerators are widely used. Recently, the concept of laser plasma acceleration (LPA) has been introduced to achieve higher acceleration gradients. These enable light charged particles, such as electrons, to be accelerated over shorter distances.

In a laser plasma accelerator, a short pulsed laser pushes electrons in the plasma to the side, creating a plasma wave. This is similar to a boat creating a wake behind it as it moves through the water. That is why this kind of accelerator is also called Laser wakefield accelerator (LWFA). This wake acts as a co-propagating acceleration cavity. Inside the cavity, an accelerating field of up to

100 GV m⁻¹ is present. If electrons from the plasma get trapped inside this cavity, they can reach energies above 100 MeV in a matter of millimeters. This allows to shrink the size of accelerators significantly, especially when aiming for multi GeV electrons. To understand the origin of these high acceleration fields and the important parameters influencing the acceleration process, the following sections will explain the most important laser parameters (2.2), the interaction between the laser and the plasma (2.3) and how to trap electrons in the cavity (2.4).

2.2 Short pulsed lasers

In laser wakefield accelerators, a single short laser pulse with high intensities is used, with a pulse duration of less than 1 ps [4]. They excite a wave in the plasma, as will be discussed in section 2.3.

To describe such a laser, the pulse properties and its diffraction have to be taken into account. This is done by solving the paraxial wave equation for electromagnetic waves. One fundamental solution to the wave equation is the Gaussian beam. The Gaussian beam is an idealized description, where the laser envelope is given by a Gaussian function. Plenty of transversal beam properties can be defined assuming the Gaussian beam. This is done by considering the Gaussian laser envelope in equation 2.1 [16], where the longitudinal profile is neglected for now.

$$\vec{E}_{\text{Gauss}}(r, z) = E_0 \vec{e}_x \frac{w_0}{w(z)} e^{-\frac{r^2}{w(z)^2}} e^{-i\left(k \frac{r^2}{2R(z)} - \psi(z)\right)} \quad (2.1)$$

Equation 2.1 considers a beam propagating in z-direction with linear polarization in x-direction. The beam parameters used to describe the Gaussian beam are:

w_0 : The **beam waist** is the distance from the laser axis to where the laser pulse intensity decreases to $1/e^2$ of its on-axis intensity, at the focus position.

z_R : The **Rayleigh length** is the distance along the z-axis where the beam waist increases to $\sqrt{2}w_0$ and is given by $z_R = \frac{\pi w_0^2}{\lambda}$.

$w(z)$: The **beam waist at z** is defined as $w(z) = w_0 \sqrt{1 + ((z - z_{\text{foc}})/z_R)^2}$.

z_{foc} : The **focus position** is the position in propagation direction, where the beam transversal diameter becomes minimal.

$R(z)$: The **curvature of the beam wavefront** is given by $R(z) = (z - z_{\text{foc}}) \left(1 + (z_R/(z - z_{\text{foc}}))^2\right)$.

$\psi(z)$: The **Gouy phase** is given by $\psi(z) = \arctan((z - z_{\text{foc}})/z_R)$.

In vacuum, the transversal width of the laser beam decreases till the laser reaches its focus position z_{foc} . Behind the focus the beam diameter increases in size. This vacuum behavior depends on the position in propagation direction and is visualized in figure 2.1. At the distance of one Rayleigh length from the focus position, the beam waist increases to $\sqrt{2}w_0$. At this point the peak intensity is reduced to half of the focus intensity.

The local intensity of a laser beam correlates with the amplitude of the electric field squared. In equation 2.1, the electric field is considered as E_0 at the focus position in the center of the beam. A common way to describe the laser intensity in simulations is by the dimensionless field strength parameter a_0 . It is given by

$$a_0 = \frac{q_e \cdot E}{m_e \cdot c \cdot \omega_0} \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2.1: Laser beam diameter evolution of a Gaussian beam during vacuum propagation.

where q_e is the charge of the electron, m_e is the electron mass, E is the electric field, ω_0 is the central laser frequency and c is the speed of light. The field strength parameter a_0 links the electric field strength of the laser to the reachable electron energy. For $a_0 = 1$ an electron reaches a kinetic energy equivalent to its rest energy in half a laser period [17]. To describe the field strength of a laser pulse, it is common practice to state the highest value of a_0 that can be reached in vacuum.

Transversal laser modes

The assumption that the transversal envelope is Gaussian is generally not true. In the beam line, the transversal envelope can be shaped by mirrors or other optical components, resulting in transverse mode patterns. To describe this transversal beam patterns, other solutions to the wave equation are needed. The laser beam needs to be described by higher modes instead of the fundamental Gaussian mode. These higher modes have an impact on the propagation of the laser in plasma and therefore also on the acceleration process of the electrons respectively [18].

The most commonly used solutions for transversal laser modes are the Hermite-Gaussian modes and the Laguerre-Gaussian modes. The Hermite-Gaussian modes recreate a square or rectangular laser shape, which is less suitable for laser plasma acceleration. The Laguerre-Gaussian modes describe a rotationally symmetric laser profile, which is a more common lasers shape [16] and more suitable for LWFA experiments. To adapt the Gaussian envelope to higher modes, the term in equation 2.4 is added, resulting in equation 2.5. L_n^m are Laguerre polynomials, where $n \geq 0$ is the radial index and m is the azimuthal index. These adaptations also lead to a solution of the paraxial wave equation [16].

$$\tilde{u}_{n,m}(z, \varphi) = \sqrt{\frac{2n!}{\pi(n + |m|)!}} e^{i((|m|+2n)\psi(z) - m\varphi)} \quad (2.3)$$

$$u_{n,m}(r, z, \varphi) = \tilde{u}_{n,m} \cdot \left(\frac{r\sqrt{2}}{w(z)} \right)^{|m|} L_n^{|m|} \left(\frac{2r^2}{w^2(z)} \right) \quad (2.4)$$

$$\vec{E}_{\text{Total}}(r, z, \varphi) = \vec{E}_{\text{Gauss}}(r, z) \sum_{n,m} \alpha_{n,m} u_{n,m}(r, z, \varphi) \quad (2.5)$$

The fundamental Gaussian beam is included in 2.5 for $m = 0$ and $n = 0$. The shape of lasers with higher order modes with increasing n and $m = 0$ is a central Gaussian beam with n concentric rings around it. For different values of n , the radial intensity distribution changes. In experiments at the DRACO laser facility, changes in the radial shape were happening in between shots while

the azimuthal structure remained stable [19, 20]. For further investigations in this thesis, the radial index n of the Laguerre polynomial will be more relevant.

Laser dispersion

The temporal shape of the laser is of interest for LPA experiments and simulations. It determines the laser-plasma interaction and thus the trapping of the electrons, as will be discussed in 2.4 and further investigated in section 5.2.2. A purely Gaussian beam also considers a Gaussian function as the envelope of the temporal laser profile. In frequency space, the temporal profile of a short laser pulse at the focus position is generally described as

$$E(z = 0, \omega) = E_\omega e^{-i\varphi}. \quad (2.6)$$

There, $E_\omega(\omega)$ describes the envelope of the frequency distribution around a central frequency ω_0 and $\varphi(\omega)$ is the phase of the beam [21].

The initial pulse shape is described by the intensity distribution as a function of the frequency and the phase of each frequency. If all frequencies have the same phase φ , then the pulse is as compressed as possible. If the phase differs for different frequencies, the pulse shape changes. A prominent and important example for such a phase displacement is the Group-delay dispersion (GDD). The Group-delay dispersion is the second order dispersion of the laser beam phase and is defined as the second derivative of the phase with respect to the frequency.

$$GDD := \left. \frac{d^2\varphi}{d\omega^2} \right|_{\omega=\omega_0} \quad (2.7)$$

In other words, GDD is the delay of the total phase with respect to the angular frequency. The unit of GDD is (time)², most commonly fs². For positive values of GDD the higher frequencies, or shorter wavelengths, have a positive phase shift. This means that the higher frequencies arrive sooner. In other words, they are located at the front of the pulse. Conversely, the lower frequencies are further back in the beam. This behavior is exactly the opposite for negative values for GDD. The phase shift leads to a broadening of the laser pulse and a decrease of the peak intensity.

Equivalently, one can define higher order dispersion, like the third order dispersion TOD. This is the third derivative of the total phase with respect to the angular frequency.

$$TOD := \left. \frac{d^3\varphi}{d\omega^3} \right|_{\omega=\omega_0} \quad (2.8)$$

If a laser pulse has TOD, the pulse duration increases and the intensity distribution over time becomes asymmetric. Even higher order dispersions have been found less relevant for LWFA experiments at DRACO and are out of scope for this work.

2.3 Acceleration principles

Under certain conditions, an electron bunch can be accelerated when a short laser pulse propagates through plasma. For this, it is necessary that the laser pulse creates a wave inside the plasma target. The electrons need to be captured in this wave and propagate behind the laser. During the propagation, the plasma interacts with the laser and alters its propagation behavior and energy. The electron bunch experiences different forces during propagation, leading to acceleration and focusing of the bunch. The following section shall be an introduction into the appearing phenomena that enable LPA and influence the acceleration process.

Exciting a plasma wave

The plasma is created from a gas with low atomic number, such as helium or hydrogen, which gets fully ionized, when the laser propagates through the plasma and the electromagnetic field of the laser interacts with the electrons of the plasma. This leads to the electrons oscillating with the frequency of the laser pulse. The electric field strength differs in transversal direction depending on the position, due to the shape of the laser envelope. Therefore, the electrons experience a stronger field towards one direction then towards the other side. The time average of this force is called the ponderomotive force \vec{F}_p and is described for non-relativistic field strengths by

$$\vec{F}_p = -\frac{q_e^2}{4m_e\omega_0^2} \vec{\nabla} E^2, \quad (2.9)$$

where q_e and m_e are the charge and mass of the electron, ω_0 and E is the angular frequency and the envelope of the amplitude of the electric field of the laser. The interpretation of this force is that charged particles experience an accelerating force toward the negative gradient of the envelope of the accelerating field, regardless of the sign of their charge. This leads the laser to push the electrons forward and to the side. While the electrons are pushed, the protons stay approximately stationary, resulting in a charge separation. This is due to the fact that the mass of the proton is about 2000 times greater than the electrons mass, which means that the ponderomotive force is suppressed by a factor of 2000, and the acceleration is even suppressed by $1/m^2$. The protons create a positive cavity behind the laser, which draws the electrons back towards the central laser axis. While moving back, the electrons gain momentum towards the central axis and overshoot. This results in a plasma oscillation with the plasma frequency ω_p given as

$$\omega_p = \sqrt{\frac{n_e \cdot q_e^2}{\epsilon_0 \cdot m_e}}, \quad (2.10)$$

where n_e is the electron density and ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, and the plasma wavelength

$$\lambda_p = \frac{2\pi c}{\omega_p}. \quad (2.11)$$

To describe the impact of the ponderomotive force, one uses the potential ψ in normalized units, which can be calculated by a second-order differential equation or numerically for a given pulse with

$$\frac{E_z}{E_0} = -\frac{c}{\omega_p} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \xi'}, \quad (2.12)$$

where ξ is the co-moving longitudinal position with the laser pulse being at $\xi = 0$ and E_z is the component of the electric field of the laser in propagation direction [17]. The description of E_z highly depends on the laser field strength. For non-relativistic cases, E_z is sinusoidal. If the laser field strength increases, E_z shows a linear increase between the first plasma wave node and the laser pulse. This description is true for an idealized case where there is no charge injected into the plasma wave and no perturbations are present. In simulations, where the electrical field components are known, E_z can be calculated on the central laser axis by integration

$$\psi(\xi) = \frac{\omega_p}{E_0 \cdot c} \int_{+\infty}^{\xi} E_z dz \quad (2.13)$$

where $E_0 = m_e c \omega_p / q_e$ is the wave-breaking field [3], assuming that the electric field in front of the laser converges to 0.

Figure 2.2: Depiction of the bubble regime. In the upper plot, the laser in green creates a wake in the plasma in black. The normalized radial focusing force is depicted in red and blue, showcasing the transversal focusing of the cavity. In the lower plot, the accelerating field in propagation direction E_z is drawn, which has an accelerating effect in the green section and decelerating in the red section. The dashed blue line corresponds to the normalized potential of the wake $\Phi(\xi) = \psi(\xi)m_e c^2/q_e$. Figure taken from [17].

LPA's are usually operated in the so-called bubble or blowout regime. This regime is characterized by a laser, which is strong enough to push all electrons aside [10]. This leaves a completely evacuated and bubble shaped cavity behind the laser with a radius $R_b \approx \lambda_p$, which is filled with positively charged ions. This effect is highly nonlinear and cannot be described by linear plasma theory anymore. It occurs for relativistic lasers with a field strength of $a_0 > 4$ [22], but also for $2 \leq a_0 \leq 4$ almost completely electron free cavities can be created [23]. These are just not quite spherical. Other than that, it is necessary for the laser to have a pulse duration shorter than the plasma cavity and the spot size has to approximately match the radius of the bubble $w_0 \approx R_p$ [24]. In the bubble regime, the focusing force applied to electrons inside the cavity is symmetrical around the central longitudinal axis.

A depiction of a wake in the bubble regime is shown in figure 2.2. In the upper part of the figure, the evacuated plasma wake can be seen in black. The cavity is surrounded by a thin layer of electrons, shielding the surrounding plasma from the cavity. Additionally, this electron layer, together with the almost stationary positively charged ions inside the cavity, create a transversal

focussing field inside the cavity. In the lower part, the accelerating and decelerating field on-axis is showcased in green and red respectively.

Self-focusing effects of the plasma

The ideal conditions for laser plasma acceleration are only fulfilled if the laser has a sufficiently high intensity. Reaching this condition at the focus position is possible with recent laser systems. But with the vacuum focusing behavior of the laser, discussed in 2.2, the intensity is reduced by a factor of two just one Rayleigh length behind the focus position. This significantly limits the reachable energy of the electron bunch, since it limits the length over which an accelerating force can be applied.

Laser propagation in plasma behaves differently than in vacuum and is in general described by the refractive index of the plasma η_p . The refractive index is not constant, but varies due to the laser plasma interaction. This leads to focusing effects that allow the laser beam to maintain a high intensity in the plasma for a longer period of time. Therefore, it is possible to accelerate the electrons for a longer period of time, resulting in higher electron energies.

The general idea of plasma self-focusing is that the refractive index on-axis, in front of the laser increases in comparison to the more outer parts of the transverse beam front because of the particle-density modulation due to the ponderomotive force. This modulation of the refractive index leads to strong focusing forces. The refractive index for an electromagnetic wave propagating in \vec{e}_z direction is given by

$$\eta = c \cdot \frac{k_z}{\omega} \quad (2.14)$$

with the wave number k_z . This corresponds to the inverse phase velocity normalized to the speed of light. The refractive index needs to be higher on-axis than off-axis in order for focusing to occur. With the dispersion relation $\omega^2 = \omega_p^2 + c^2 k^2$ of an electromagnetic wave, the refractive index becomes

$$\eta(r) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega_p^2(r)}{\omega^2}}. \quad (2.15)$$

From 2.15 it is obvious, that for increasing ω_p the refractive index η decreases. The case of vacuum propagation is also included, where $\omega_p = 0$ and η becomes 1. The laser applies a ponderomotive force onto the plasma altering the electron density in front of the laser from n_0 to $n(r)$ and increases the kinetic energy of the electrons to a relativistic level with a Lorentz-factor of $\gamma_e(r)$. This modifies the plasma frequency 2.10 to

$$\omega_p(r) = \omega_{p,0} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{n(r)}{\gamma_e(r)n_0}}. \quad (2.16)$$

The ponderomotive force has the highest impact on the laser axis, leading to the smallest electron density $n(r)$ and the highest Lorentz factor $\gamma_e(r)$ for $r = 0$. Both of these effects lead to a decrease of $\omega_p(r)$, which in turn leads to an increase of $\eta(r)$ for $r \approx 0$. This results in a refractive index maximum at the center of the beam, leading to a lower phase velocity there compared to the outer part, which consequently focuses the laser [4, 17].

Due to this self-focusing effect, the defraction of the laser can be delayed and continues driving of the wake is possible. Therefore, higher electron energies can be reached.

2.4 Injection mechanism

So far it has been discussed how to create and drive a plasma wave, how to contain the wave and which fields are present inside the plasma wave. To use this plasma wave as an electron accelerator, electrons need to be injected into the plasma cavity. In current LWFA experiments, three different injection methods are commonly used. These are wave-breaking injection, density transition injection and ionization injection, each of which injects electrons from the plasma into the plasma wave cavity.

Wave-breaking injection operates in the blowout regime, where at the back of the cavity high electron densities are present and the accelerating field E_z has a minimum. There, electrons can be spontaneously injected into the cavity and experience a strong accelerating field which further moves them into the cavity. Once in the bubble, the electrons co-propagate behind the laser and continuously experience the accelerating field and get accelerated as long as the blowout regime can be maintained [10].

Density transition injection exploits the dependency of the cavity size on the plasma density. A density gradient is created in the plasma density profile, for example by placing a wire or wedge inside the gas nozzle. Due to this steep gradient in plasma density, the plasma frequency decreases (see equation 2.10). This causes the plasma wavelength to increase and the bubble to expand. During this process, the rear of the bubble shifts farther upstream. As a result, electrons that were initially at the back of the cavity are left inside the cavity and are trapped [25].

Ionization injection utilizes a doped plasma, taking advantage of the distinct ionization energies of the doping gas. The doping gas consists of atoms with a higher atomic number Z , often nitrogen, and is added in a small ratio to the plasma. Inner shell electrons of the doping gas are ionized at higher laser intensities, which other electrons cannot reach due to the ponderomotive force. From there they can be captured within the plasma cavity rather than oscillate around the beam axis. The main advantage of this method, is that the necessary laser intensity and plasma density can be decreased [26, 27] compared to the wave-breaking injection. Additionally, ionization injection showed promising results regarding the total charge and controllability of the resulting electron beam, as it has been shown at HZDR [19]. This injection method will be examined in more detail in the remainder of this thesis and is explained in more detail below.

Ionization injection

Ionization injection was first experimentally confirmed by Pak et al. [27] and McGuffey et al. [26]. To operate an LPA with ionization injection, the plasma consists of a low- Z atoms like helium or hydrogen and high- Z atoms as doping. A commonly used high- Z atom is nitrogen. The electrons of the low- Z gas and the outer shell electrons of the doping gas get ionized initially when they interact with the laser. Then the ponderomotive force acts on them, and they create the plasma wave. The inner shell electrons of the doping constituents have higher ionization energies and are therefore ionized further towards the center of the laser where the laser intensity is higher. There they experience a force, which may not push them sideways or forward and into the plasma wave as the outer shell electrons, but keep them inside the bubble and trap them. For trapping, in addition to the fact that the ionization energy must be reached by the laser, two further conditions must be met.

Firstly, any transversal momentum that the electrons gain between ionization and trapping in the cavity must be compensated. In the bubble regime, this is ensured by the azimuthal magnetic field, which applies a focusing force on relativistic electrons.

Secondly, the ionized electrons need to reach a sufficiently high kinetic energy to be able to keep up with the plasma wave. Under the assumption that the electrons have no momentum immediately after ionization, their momentum in the propagation direction depends only on the

accelerating force E_z . Initially, they are accelerated in opposite direction to the laser propagation, until they reach the center of the bubble and experience an accelerating field in laser propagation direction, as visualized in figure 2.2. They can be captured only if the electrons reach the phase velocity of the plasma wave before they reach the end of the bubble. To quantify this condition, in one dimension for a given electric field E_z , one can use the potential Ψ calculated by equation 2.13. The difference of the potential at the point of ionization Ψ_i and the final position of the electron Ψ_f , $\Delta\Psi = \Psi_f - \Psi_i$, must satisfy [17] :

$$\Delta\Psi \leq -1. \quad (2.17)$$

This condition is illustrated in figure 2.3, where the green area corresponds to the region where trapping is possible and orange to the area where trapping is impossible.

Figure 2.3: Illustration of the trapping condition of ionization injection. If ionization occurs in the green region, as for Ψ_i^{II} , trapping is possible. In the orange region as for Ψ_i^I trapping is not possible. The red line depicts the laser envelope in units of the field strength parameter a_0 and the blue dashed line is the corresponding potential Ψ . Figure taken from [17].

One fundamental disadvantage of ionization injection is that once the ionization energy of the inner shell electrons of the doping is reached, the ionization process continues during the whole time the laser propagates in the plasma and is intense enough. This continuous injection leads to a high energy spread of the electron bunch. To mitigate this, it is advantageous to limit the duration of the ionization process, effectively truncating the injection.

Truncation of the injection process

Various different mechanisms have been proposed to limit the ionization injection and prevent a high energy spread. Examples include the use of dual-stage targets, where the doping is only present for a limited region, a combination of a density transition and ionization injection [28] and self-truncated ionization injection (STII) [29]. The latter is particularly easy to operate, requiring no additional modifications to the gas target, and has been experimentally demonstrated to generate quasi-monoenergetic electron beams with a high charge [19].

Achieving self-truncation requires control over the evolution of the laser intensity and the plasma cavity shape. This can be accomplished by introducing a laser with an unmatched spot size, meaning the spot size does not correspond to the dimensions of the plasma cavity. This is done by focusing the laser deeper into the plasma, more than one Rayleigh length, so that it enters the plasma in an unfocused and less intense state. The intensity is too small to ionize the inner shell electrons. Only close to the focus position, the intensity is high enough to ionize and inject. After the focus, the laser refracts and reduces in intensity, which stops the injection again [19]. While this uses the intensity modulation of the laser, another approach is to use the wakefield evolution which breaks the trapping condition at some point. Again an unmatched laser is used, which initially fulfills the trapping condition. When self-focusing effects occur, the laser amplitude increases and the laser reaches the required ionization energy further in the front of the cavity, at the potential ψ_i . At some point, ψ_i is so far in the front of the cavity that the trapping condition $\Delta\psi \leq -1$ is no longer satisfied [29].

Another effect that leads to self-truncation of the injection is the increase in potential at the end of the cavity ψ_f due to the injected charge itself. If charge is injected the accelerating field E_z decreases there, due to Coulomb repulsion and consequently the potential ψ_f increases. The trapping condition of $\Delta\psi \leq -1$ cannot be fulfilled anymore, and injection stops.

2.5 Measurement of the electron bunch properties

The aim of this work includes reproducing experimental electron beams with simulations and gaining insight into the underlying physics. To achieve this, it is necessary to know the quantities measured in experiments and how to calculate them from simulation results.

In experiments at the HZDR Laser facility DRACO [30], the electron beam properties are measured in an electron spectrometer. In this spectrometer, the energy, energy spread, charge and divergence can be measured. The electron spectrometer consists mainly of a magnetic dipole, scintillator screens and cameras to image the screens. To measure the energy, the electron bunch is deflected by the magnetic field of the dipole and directed to the scintillator screens. There, according to the Lorentz force $F = q \cdot (\vec{v} \times \vec{B})$, the electrons are deflected in a radius depending on their velocity or momentum respectively. After they passed through the dipole field, they hit the scintillator screen. From the position, where the electrons hit the scintillator screen, the energy of the electrons can be determined via a calibration process [31].

The divergence is a measure of the statistical transversal spreading of the electron beam. Each electron has a transversal deflection angle θ and hits the scintillator screen at a certain distance from center. From the distribution of the transversal spread of the electrons on the screen, the divergence can be determined.

The scintillator screen consists of a 10 μm to 100 μm thin layer of rare earth phosphor and is commonly known under the name LANEX [31]. Once an electron hits the scintillator screen, it deposits some of its energy, which is converted into visible light by fluorescence. The visible light from the scintillator screen is captured by a camera. Through a calibration process, explained in detail in [32], the scintillator light is converted to the charge per surface area of the scintillator screen.

The resulting output of the electron spectrometer shows the charge distribution per energy and deflection angle $\frac{d^2Q}{dE d\theta}$. From this, various beam properties can be calculated, like energy spread and total charge.

Deriving the same information in simulations can be done, since the momentum $\vec{p} = (p_x, p_y, p_z)^T$ of each modeled electron is known. With the absolute value p of the momentum, the relativistic

energy of a single particle can be calculated by

$$E = \sqrt{(m_e c^2)^2 + (pc)^2} - m_e c^2 \quad (2.18)$$

where m_e is the mass of the electron and c the speed of light.

The transversal deflection angle θ is the angle between electron propagation in laser polarization direction and laser propagation direction. It is calculated by

$$\theta = \arctan \left(\frac{p_x}{p_z} \right) \quad (2.19)$$

where p_x is the momentum in polarization direction and p_z the momentum in laser propagation direction. The divergence is then the spread of the distribution of θ .

With these two values for each electron, a two-dimensional histogram is created and multiplied by the electron charge, resulting in the charge distribution $\frac{d^2Q}{dE d\theta}$.

3 Automating particle-in-cell simulations

Particle-in-cell (PIC) simulations are a method of solving a system of partial differential equations that can be better solved by splitting the variables into groups of spatially static and spatially varying variables and solving each subsystem independently. An example is the Maxwell-Vlasov equation, where the magnetic and electric field values are evaluated at fixed points in space, while the distribution function $f(x)$ is treated as an ensemble of particles moving freely in space. Particularly laser plasma accelerators with their non-linear plasma dynamic benefit from this simulation algorithm. In this thesis, PIC-simulations will be used to recreate experimental results and gain a deeper understanding of the dependencies of LWFA on certain laser and plasma parameters. For the simulation study presented here, the simulation software PIconGPU [33], which is a PIC code developed at HZDR, is used. In section 3.1, of this chapter, the particle-in-cell cycle is introduced. Running a simulation requires several steps, which depend on each other. For the execution of many simulations, as required for parameter scans, these tasks are very repetitive and time-consuming. This repetition provides the possibility of automation. In this thesis, a workflow which automated the necessary tasks was developed using a workflow engine. An introduction to workflow engines is given in section 3.2, and a detailed description of what is automated and how the workflow was implemented is given in section 3.3.

3.1 The particle-in-cell method

Particle-in-cell (PIC) simulations are the tool of choice to model laser plasma accelerators. Plasma simulation must calculate the trajectories of 10^7 to 10^8 particles and the evolution of the electromagnetic field, which comes with high computational costs. For this reason, assumptions are made that simplify the calculations. The fields are discretized on a lattice. The particles can move freely in the grid. Since particles at a similar position and with similar momentum result in similar trajectories, they are combined into macro-particles. This simplifies calculations and does not significantly affect the accuracy.

For a physically correct charged particle distribution and electromagnetic fields, the time evolution of the particle position and the electromagnetic fields is calculated using the PIC cycle. The PIC cycle consists of four steps and is depicted in figure 3.1. The first step of the algorithm is the calculation of the force. The current electromagnetic field is used to calculate the force acting on each macroparticle. Next, the particles are propagated according to the current force. The propagating particles cause an electric current, which is calculated in the third step. The current

has an impact on the electric and magnetic field, according to the Maxwell equations. After the electric current is calculated, the electric and magnetic fields must be calculated, which is the fourth and last step before the cycle restarts.

Figure 3.1: Depiction of the four steps of the PIC-cycle. \vec{E} and \vec{B} are the electric and magnetic field and \vec{F} is the corresponding Lorentz force. q , \vec{v} and \vec{p}_i is the charge, velocity and momentum of a particle at time step i , Δt is the duration of one time step, $f(\vec{r}, \vec{v})$ is the distribution function of the particles and \vec{j} is the electric current. Figure is adapted from [17].

One designated PIC-code for laser plasma acceleration is developed at HZDR. The code is called PIconGPU, which stands for "particle-in-cell on graphic-compute-units".

3.2 An overview of workflow engines

Workflow engines are in general a software tool to automate multiple task which depend on each other. These task can be anything from computational tasks, to data handling or visualization. Workflows are particularly useful when these tasks need to be performed multiple times in the same or similar way.

The main goal of a workflow engine is to automate a sequence of different tasks. The dependencies between these tasks can be arbitrary complex and can also include exceptions, for instance if a task fails in the middle of the workflow. Each task might need different resources, which the workflow engine can allocate independent of the computer system, where the workflow is executed. Workflow engines manage task scheduling, simplify parallel task execution and can therefore help to reduce the overall resource requirements. Additionally, the necessary data management can be completely handled by the workflow engine. The workflow engine also tracks the execution of each single task and provides metadata and all required information to reproduce the workflow output.

The advantages of workflow engines, compared to manual task execution, are significant. Due to their generalized definition, they can be shared between users with similar task, for example between scientist in a research group. Furthermore, workflow engines inherently enhance the reproducibility of data generation and evaluation processes.

To execute PIconGPU simulations several steps are required, which are further explained in section 3.3.1, making it an ideal use case for automatization. Until now, the execution of several simulations has been realized individually by each user for each application. These individual solutions cannot be easily shared between users and lack most of the benefits a workflow engine could supply. Now, a unified workflow exists, that allows easy sharing.

There are many available workflow engine, which support workflows with different demands. Selecting a suitable workflow engine for the present use case of executing PIConGPU simulations is an important aspect of designing the workflow. First and foremost, cluster execution needs to be supported. In addition, the interface should be relatively simple to keep the barrier to entry low for the user. It is particular beneficial to select a workflow engine which has a user base in the anticipated field, who natively can use the workflow and supply support and feedback to the workflow. With these criteria in mind, the workflow engine Snakemake [34] was selected. Snakemake already has a user base at HZDR and is python based. Python, being the most common programming language to evaluate PIConGPU data, is a great choice for an interface for the workflow. Snakemake is compatible with various job schedulers and supports the execution of jobs on different clusters. For example, Slurm, which is the scheduler of the HZDR internal cluster hemera, is supported among many others.

Snakemake is suitable for workflows, which are representable as a directed acyclic graph (DAG). The dependencies of the individual tasks in Snakemake are defined by input and output files. A detailed description of the usage of Snakemake as a workflow engine for PIConGPU simulations is given in 3.3.2.

3.3 Automating parallel execution of multiple simulations

Three-dimensional, realistic, large scale simulations can require a huge amount of compute resources and cannot simply be performed on a desktop PC. Usually they are executed on high-performance computing (HPC) systems, where the resources need to be requested and scheduled. The scheduling is done by a job scheduler, which can be different for different compute cluster.

The aim is to provide a reusable tool, which allows to run many simulations in parallel. Additionally, this tool should be easy to use and easily adjustable to various applications. To get an understanding why this is beneficial, an overview about the required steps to start a PIConGPU simulation is given in 3.3.1. The concrete implementation of the workflow is outlined in section 3.3.2 and an outlook on the possible applications is given in section 3.3.3.

3.3.1 Set up and run a PIConGPU simulation

With a PIConGPU simulations, physical scenarios like laser plasma interactions are modeled. This scenario must be defined, which is done in standardized parameter files. The physical properties of the scenario and the numerical settings of the simulation are set there. These range from plasma and laser parameters to the grid resolution, the used field solver and particle pusher to very general properties like dimensionality of the simulation. All of these are compile time parameters, meaning they need to be defined prior to compiling. Defining the physical scenario in the PIConGPU parameter files is the most difficult and time-consuming part of setting up a simulation. The particular parameters differ a lot between applications. Therefore, an automatization of this step is impossible. Fortunately, often times several simulations with one defined physics setup are performed, where only a few parameters are changed. In these cases, automatization is beneficial. To only alter single parameters, it is not necessary to make large changes in the parameter files, and it is possible to change a limited number of values using CMake flags, which are passed at compile time.

Once the physical scenario is defined, the code must be compiled for exactly those parameters and hardware. This significantly improves runtime performance. On most clusters, compiling cannot be done on the head node because the compute resources available there are insufficient for compiling. Then cluster resources need to be requested, and the user needs to wait till they are allocated and manually start the compile process. The compilation itself, takes between five and

twenty minutes, depending on the complexity of the setup. This is very repetitive and independent of the set-up and underlying physics and can therefore be automated.

Before starting the simulation, run time information need to be set. These include for instance the size of the simulation box, the duration of the simulation, the definition of all output which shall be generated and saved and most importantly all required cluster resources for the simulation. The definition of run time parameters are done in a configuration file. Of course this definition is highly individual and needs to be modified for every case. But in large parameter scans, the resources are the same for every simulation and do not hinder automatization.

To start the simulations, the template batch generator (tbg), which is an integrated tool of PIconGPU, is used. This generator takes the system independent run time information and a system dependent template file and combines them to a submit-script and optionally submits it to the cluster right away. The template file stores information about the system architecture and is for many large scale computer systems already included in PIconGPU.

The automation should include submitting the simulation to the cluster. A crucial question was whether the tbg tool should be reused or not. The advantage of using tbg is that, with the existing template files, the description of some HPC systems is already done and can be used. On the other hand some workflow engines also grant a machine independent cluster execution schema, which would also allow to abstract the resource acquisition to different HPC systems. Using the workflow engine for resource acquisition is beneficial because it would enable the engine to have full control over submitting, canceling, and error handling of each job. But it would require to redo the tbg abstraction which was already implemented for several HPC systems. For code reusability, it was decided to reuse the tbg code and search for solutions in section 3.3.2 to still permit the workflow engine to have good control over the job handling.

To conclude, each simulation requires a huge amount of individual definitions in order to model the anticipated physical scenario. In particular the definition of the physical and numerical set up and the resources and output definition. This cannot be automated. Once these things are set, the rest is very repetitive and offers the possibility of automation. How this was implemented is described in detail in the next section.

3.3.2 Implementing an abstract workflow for PIconGPU simulations

The goal of using the workflow engine with PIconGPU is to allow the user to start all the tasks necessary for a simulation with a single command. This was achieved with the Python-based, open source library Snakemake [34]. The implementation of workflow consists of a Snakefile, which describes the workflow, a configuration file, which defines the user specific dependencies and resources and a parameter file, which specifies the parameters which shall be altered. The Snakefile defines four rules, which are called:

- `build_command`
- `compile`
- `simulate`
- `all`

Each rule is the description of a distinct task, which is either done via an external script, shell commands or python code. The rules abstract the task that are necessary to compile and run a simulation. The order in which the tasks are executed is determined by their input and output files.

The first rule is called `build_command` and is a helper for the compilation. In this rule, a string

is created for each instance of input parameters from the parameter file. This rule converts the name and value of each parameter to a string that can be interpreted by the PICongPU compiler as CMake flags and can be used in the compile process.

The second rule is called `compile` and handles the compilation of the simulations. Since compiling requires cluster resources, the workflow engine request resources using Snakemakes internal cluster abstraction and waits till they are allocated to start the compile process. For that, it copies a predefined physical scenario, the location of which is defined via the configuration file by the user. Then it takes the string which was created with the `build_command` rule and executes the compilation using the string to transfer the parameters as CMake flags to the simulation. Afterwards the `tbg` method is used to create a submit-script with the predefined PICongPU run time parameters.

Once this is finished, the third rule is executed, which starts and monitors the simulation. This rule is called `simulate`. Since it was decided to use the `tbg` method to translate the required resources for the simulation from the cluster independent definition to the cluster-specific definition, the workflow engine does not request the cluster resources for this rule. Instead, it submits the simulation to the cluster with the submit script created by `tbg`. Then, it watches the status of the submitted job and waits till the job is finished. The biggest disadvantage of this method is that Snakemake's error handling cannot be used. This means that if the simulation fails, the workflow aborts and has to be restarted manually. Similarly, if the workflow engine crashes, the monitoring loop is aborted and Snakemake loses reference to the simulation job. To avoid this, it is possible to define in the Snakefile how often a simulation should be automatically restarted in case of a crash. In order to continue monitoring a simulation in the event of a workflow engine crash, the job ID of the cluster job is saved and retrieved when the workflow engine is restarted. The monitoring of the submitted job rule is specific for the scheduler of the cluster. Therefore, this rule needs to be adapted to different schedulers. So far, a Snakefile for clusters with Slurm or LSF scheduler are available in PICongPU.

The last rule is called `all`, which is the so-called target rule and necessary for all Snakemake workflows. In this rule, the anticipated output is defined. In this specific case, this is a file which is created once the simulation succeeded. This rule does not perform any specific task, its purpose is to control which tasks are performed and which are not.

To visualize the presented workflow, an exemplary graph is depicted in figure 3.2. This is created for a parameter file including values for the laser strength a_0 and the pulse duration of the laser beam. The parameter file can look like this

```
A0, PULSEDURATION
4.0, 1.5e-14
3.0, 2.5e-14
```

and would trigger the execution of two simulations. The two simulations would be performed in parallel, in a sense that they would be started at the same time but with distinct resources. Additional parameters can be varied, or new simulations can be initiated by simply modifying the input file.

3.3.3 Possible use cases and adaptations for the workflow

The workflow presented here is very general, but can be used as a basis for more specialized applications. The trivial case is to set up large parameter scans instantly. Other conceivable

Figure 3.2: Graph representation of the workflow implementation for two exemplary parameters.

applications include scaling tests and optimization campaigns. For the first of these two, run time parameters of the simulation need be altered which requires some minor tweaks to the Snakefile and the rule compile would not need to be executed for every set of runtime parameters. For the optimization campaign, Snakemake's restriction to acyclic dependencies is a constraint, but the individual simulations can still be run more easily and the evaluation and optimization step can be integrated into the workflow, which reduces the user's workload and possible waiting times.

Some physical scenarios also might require several steps before running the simulation. Examples for this can be: reading experimentally measured laser field data and using it for the simulation or defining an electron bunch and using that to excite a plasma wake. These kinds of simulations could also be generalized and automated with the workflow engine.

It is possible to expand the workflow with an arbitrary amount of tasks. The most common adaptation is to expand the workflow with the post-processing of the simulation output. This is very beneficial because Snakemake allows multiple rules to be grouped into one cluster job, minimizing the number of small individual jobs and thus reducing the workload on the scheduler. If the simulations output is large, Snakemake can also be used to delete all or parts of the simulation output once the post-processing is done. For the use case of parameter optimization, which will be used in chapter 4, the workflow can wait till all simulations are run and just then carry out the optimization algorithm once all needed data is collected. The dependencies can be arbitrary complex and could also depend on the simulations output or post-processing results. In summary, a framework for using a workflow engine with PICongPU has been implemented. This simplifies many applications of PICongPU simulations and automates their analysis and handling of the generated data in a reproducible way.

4 A systematic approach to reproduce experiments via simulation

4.1 Addressing the difficulties of reproducing experiments in simulations

One of the main purposes of executing large scale laser plasma simulations, is to gain a deeper understanding of the laser plasma interactions of experimental LPA scenarios. Therefore, it is necessary to model the realistic laser plasma interaction and electron acceleration process as accurate as possible, which poses plenty of difficulties. It would be necessary to have a complete description of all laser and plasma settings from the experimental side and a correct physical and numerical implementation and calculation on the simulation side to recreate an experiment in a PIC simulation. Both of which is hard to reach if not impossible.

In experiments, it is hard to measure every parameter. Measurements of the laser intensity, phase, or dispersion can be destructive and are therefore cannot necessarily be made simultaneously with laser plasma acceleration. In between shots, the laser parameters in particular the dispersion change constantly and are therefore not exactly determined. Plasma parameter can be even harder to measure. One way to estimate the density profile of the plasma is to image the plasma wake using shadowgraphy, measure the plasma wavelength, and calculate the density. This only holds true if a plasma wave can be excited. Simulating the density distribution generated by the supersonic gas nozzle is another option. But this requires several assumptions to be made, such as assuming an ideal gas and that the flow is frictionless. In reality, even tiny imperfections or changes to the nozzle can lead to deviations between the simulation and reality. Most experimental parameters can be determined and adjusted, but always involve measuring uncertainty.

Also on the simulation side, not everything can be modelled to represent reality. Simulations always suffer from numerical issues. The finer the temporal and spatial resolution of the simulation, the smaller the numerical error but the greater the need for computing resources. Additionally, not every parameter or parameter combination is adjustable in PIConGPU yet. For instance, it is currently not possible to use a laser with transversal modes and temporal dispersion in a single simulation. To reduce the latter problem, the development of PIC codes is an ongoing task. For instance in PIConGPU it has recently become possible to read measured laser data into the simulation and therefore allow to recreate the exact measured temporal and spatial laser profile.

Here, an approach is presented to recreate experiments via PIConGPU simulations, despite all the uncertainties introduced by the experimental measurements and the simplifications on

which the simulation is based. The aim is to find the parameters where the simulation and the experiment agree best. To find these parameters, one could scan the entire parameter space in question and select the closest result, but this would require a tremendous amount of resources and time. In order to simulate the experiment with as little computational effort as possible, an optimization algorithm is used to select the most promising parameter points for the next simulation until an optimum is found.

4.2 Using optimization algorithms to model Laser plasma acceleration

Achieving optimized electron bunch properties, with as few as possible simulations or experimental shots, is a topic of growing interest in the laser particle acceleration community. Already in 2020, Shaloo et al. applied Bayesian optimization to LWFA experiments and were able to optimize the divergence of the electron beam and total beam energy and by that creating a fully automated plasma accelerator [35]. Bayesian optimization has proven to be a powerful tool for LPA simulations in order to optimize certain electron bunch properties [36, 37].

Here the aim is to recreate measured electron spectra, and not to optimize single electron bunch properties. Finding an optimum that represents the experiment is a necessity to investigate which physical processes take place in the experiment. In particular, the subsequent step in chapter 5 is to investigate which parameters the electron beam reacts sensitively to. Recreating the experimental electron spectra was achieved by exploiting the Bayesian optimization algorithm, which is introduced in section 4.2.1. The specific realization of Bayesian optimization to the modelling of LPA experiments with PIConGPU simulations is described in 4.2.2.

4.2.1 Introduction to Bayesian optimization

Bayesian optimization makes it possible to find the optimum of a function with as few evaluations of the function as possible. This is in particular useful for functions, which are difficult or expensive to evaluate. The goal of Bayesian optimization is to find the extremum of an objective function $t(x)$. The objective function defines the goal of the optimization, in general the parameter that shall be maximized or minimized. The specific definition of the objective function $t(x)$ is therefore crucial for the success of the optimization [36]. Mathematical speaking, the objective function needs to be a scalar function but can depend on up to 20 parameters [38].

To find the optimum of the objective function, the Bayesian optimization algorithm is applied on some initial sampling points. The initial sampling shall minimize the initial uncertainty of the model [39]. It is useful to use pseudo-random sample points, such as those provided by a Halton sequence [40] or latin hypercube sampling [41]. They cover the space more evenly than random parameters and sample individual parameters more densely than grid sampling. Latin hypercube sampling, for example, divides the parameter space into multiple equal intervals and generates a point in each interval to ensure equal sampling.

Latin hypercube sampling (LHS) is a statistical method for generating a near-random sample of parameter combinations, ensuring that the range of each parameter is evenly sampled by dividing it into intervals and selecting one value from each interval in a stratified manner.

The algorithm for finding the next best parameter to evaluate is shown in Figure 4.1, as an example for an objective function $t(x)$ that depends on a scalar parameter x . From the evaluated sampling points, a surrogate model is created. It is common to use a Gaussian process as a surrogate for Bayesian optimization. A Gaussian process f is a stochastic process in which, for each value x , the function values $f(x)$ are random variables that are normal distributed [42]. The Gaussian process is fully defined by its mean function $\mu_{\text{GP}}(x)$ and the covariance function $\sigma_{\text{GP}}(x)$.

Bayesian optimization assumes an a priori Gaussian process, for which the covariance function is defined by a kernel function and a constant mean value. The kernel function can be freely selected and defines the rate and the amplitude of the variations of the functions sampled by the Gaussian process. It takes two parameters x and x' as an input and calculates the covariance between these two points. Then the distribution of the random values $f(x_1), \dots, f(x_n)$ is jointly normal with constant mean μ and has a covariance matrix with entries determined by the kernel function evaluated at the sampling points x_1, \dots, x_n .

Under the assumption that x_1, \dots, x_n and their function values $t(x_1), \dots, t(x_n)$ are known the conditional distribution $f(x)$ of the function value $t(x)$ of an arbitrary parameter x is normally distributed. The standard deviation of $f(x) | t(x_1), \dots, t(x_n)$ is calculated from the covariance matrix and the mean depends on the function values $t(x_1), \dots, t(x_n)$ and the covariance matrix [43].

Once the surrogate is determined an acquisition function is calculated. The acquisition function serves as the strategy to determine the next parameter to sample. There exist a variety of acquisition functions. Prominent examples are the expected improvement function, the upper and lower confident bound and the probability of improvement function, along many more [37]. The acquisition function controls whether the algorithm focuses more on exploiting the existing points, thus focusing on the mean function, or whether the algorithm focuses more on exploration, taking into account the uncertainties of the Gaussian process. The lower confidence bound (LCB) is a simple example for an acquisition function, where the objective is supposed to be minimized.

$$LCB(x) = \mu_{GP}(x) - \kappa \cdot \sigma_{GP}(x) \quad (4.1)$$

The LCB function weights the mean prediction $\mu_{GP}(x)$ and the covariance prediction $\sigma_{GP}(x)$ using the parameter κ [42]. With κ , the balance between exploration and exploitation can be set. The minimum of the LCB function is the next best parameter sample, as shown in figure 4.1 with a blue dot in each subplot. The objective function is then evaluated at this next best query point and with the new evaluated point the algorithm starts over again. This process is repeated till the minimum of the objective converges or until the resources for evaluating the objective function are exhausted.

4.2.2 Applying Bayesian optimization to Laser plasma acceleration

Objective

The choice of the objective is crucial for the optimization result and depends strongly on the goal of the optimization [36]. Here, Bayesian optimization shall be used to recreate an experimental electron bunch. The experimental electron bunch is defined by the measured electron spectrometer, as described in section 2.5, since it is the only available information about the electron bunch. The spectrometers to be used as target functions are shown in figure 4.2. The challenge is now to find a measure for how closely the simulated and an experimentally measured electron spectrometer are related. As mentioned before, the objective function needs to be a scalar function and the output from the electron spectrometer is a two-dimensional histogram. Prior objective function with application in LPA included considering the total counts on the electron spectrometer [35], which is not suitable to optimize for distinct electron beam parameters. Additionally, it was found in [36], that is beneficial to optimize for concrete target values, instead of trying to maximize or minimize a certain value.

The specific aim here is to get as close as possible to the experimental beam parameters. Therefore, it appears reasonable to use as much information as possible from the spectrometer. For that purpose, the average of the target spectrometer output of figure 4.2 was calculated and simplified. The resulting spectrometer is shown in the top of figure 4.3 and will, from now on, be called target spectrum. The scalar objective value is calculated for an arbitrary simulated electron

Figure 4.1: Bayesian optimization algorithm for an objective function (orange) depending on a scalar parameter x . The three pictures correspond to three iterations of the algorithm, where in each step one further point is evaluated. The next query point (blue) is determined as the minimum of the acquisition function (dark green). In this case the lower confidence bound $LCB(x) = \mu_{GP}(x) - \kappa \cdot \sigma_{GP}(x)$, where $\kappa = 1.96$ is chosen as the acquisition function. The mean μ (dashed green) and the confidence interval σ (light green) are determined by a Gaussian process.

spectrum as follows. First the simulated spectra is binned within exactly the same energy ranges and angular range as the target spectrum and with the same bin widths. These ranges are from 100 to 500 MeV and from -20 to 20 mrad and in each dimension 500 equidistant bins were used. Then, the absolute value of the difference of these two spectra is calculated. For visualization purposes this is shown in the bottom of 4.3. Each bin of this resulting two-dimensional histogram is then summed up to a single scalar number, which will be used as the objective.

The objective presented here combines optimization for energy, divergence, and charge. For charge outside the target spectrometer, the objective will increase, and for charge within the target area, the objective will decrease until the charge of the target is exceeded, then the objective will increase again. A possible pitfall of this definition is the case of no injection. Then, only the bins of the target spectra are summed, and there is no charge outside the target region to increase the objective. This leads to an objective value of 6895, which is comparatively small and in the worst case leads to an optimization towards no injection at all. To avoid this, one could weight this objective by the total injected charge, which could alter the optimization significantly. Here, the parameter space in which the optimization takes place is chosen narrow enough the case of no injection does not occur.

Figure 4.2: Experimental electron spectrometer from experimental campaign in 2019. Experiments were conducted at HZDR with the DRACO laser. The results shown here are representative of a desirable electron bunch, with high charge and low divergence.

Implementing Optimization into the simulation workflow

To implement the Bayesian optimization algorithm, the open source python module scikit-optimize was used. There, the "Optimizer" class is used in order to calculate the surrogate model using a Gaussian process. As an acquisition function, the lower confidence bound, which was defined in equation 4.1, was used. The hyperparameter κ was left at the default of 1.96, set by scikit-optimize.

Initially, 10 start parameters were determined using latin hypercube sampling. For each of these parameter points, a simulation is carried out and afterwards the corresponding objective was calculated. The parameters and the corresponding objective are stored in a csv (comma-separated values) file. With these 10 objective values the Bayesian algorithm is performed, and the next values are determined. All evaluation steps are included in a workflow and executed automatically. The next parameter points are also stored in csv file and can be immediately used to start the next workflow and obtain the next objective and thus the next query point.

As explained previously in section 4.2.1, the Bayesian optimization suggests the next best query point. This means that each simulation must be executed one after the other. Since each simulation takes several hours to complete, such a sequential process is not time efficient. The implementation of the Bayesian optimization algorithm in scikit-optimize can predict more than one new parameter at a time, which is beneficial because it allows more than one simulation to be run in parallel, saving time. For this, the algorithm first predicts only one new query point x_{next} and then assumes that the objective for x_{next} will be exactly $\mu_{\text{GP}}(x_{\text{next}})$. Then, the Bayesian optimization algorithm is re-run with the new assumed pair of values and proposes another new query point. This was used to predict 2 to 3 new parameter points and thus run 2 to 3 simulations in parallel. It has been found that requesting more than 2 to 3 next query points can lead to unfavorable results. This is because if the next best query point is chosen where the uncertainty is high, the assumption $t(x_{\text{next}}) = \mu_{\text{GP}}(x_{\text{next}})$, where t is the objective function, has a large error and can mislead the optimization, leading to multiple simulations far from the true optimum.

Figure 4.3: Definition of the objective function for the optimization of the simulation to the experiment. The upper plot is the target spectrum and is the simplified experimental electron spectra from the experiments shown in figure 4.2. The spectrum in the middle is an example of a simulated electron spectrum. The lowest spectrum shows the absolute difference between the upper two. The summation of all the bins of the lowest row results in the objective for this simulation. For this example the objective is 7451.

4.3 Tailoring the simulation setup

As described in section 3.3.1, defining a simulation setup is the most difficult and time-consuming part of running a PIconGPU simulation. The setup definition for the recreation of the experimental electron spectrum with the Bayesian optimization algorithm is briefly summarized in section 4.3.1 and the suitability of this setup for reproducing the experimental results is discussed. Additionally, not all necessary parameters are known as discussed in section 4.1. Therefore, it is almost always necessary to iteratively adjust the simulation setup in consultation with the experimentalists to find the setup that agrees with the experimental results. This was the case here, and these adjustments are described in 4.3.2 and the final result is described in section 4.3.3.

4.3.1 Initial setup

For each parameter set, a realistic three-dimensional PIconGPU simulation was performed. Each simulation modeled a short-pulse laser propagating through a plasma, driving a plasma wake, and subsequently accelerating electrons. The simulation volume has a size of $(136.1 \times 136.1 \times 89.3) \mu\text{m}$. The simulation volume moves with the laser during the simulation. The resolution in transversal direction is $0.177 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.023 \mu\text{m}$ in longitudinal direction. To solve the Maxwell-equations on the grid the Lehe solver [44] was used. For the current deposition the Esirkepov schema [45] and for the particle push the Boris pusher [46] was used. The particles per cell were set to two.

The plasma target is modelled by a one-dimensional plasma density profile leading to a homogeneous density in the transversal plane and an approximately super-Gaussian shape in longitudinal direction. The plasma profile is based on a measurement of the plasma density generated by a gas nozzle during experiments at HZDR. The base density of this measured and modelled profile is about $4 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The plasma consists of 96 % helium and 4 % nitrogen.

The laser was modeled to represent the titanium-sapphire laser DRACO at HZDR. Therefore, a pulse duration of 30 fs and a central wavelength of 800 nm were used. The shape of the laser is not purely Gaussian, but has some transversal radial Gaussian-Laguerre modes. The composition of modes is summarized in table 4.1. This composition was obtained by a reconstruction of a measurement of the transversal laser profile of the DRACO laser.

Table 4.1: Contribution $\alpha_{n,0}$ of each radial Laguerre mode n to the total laser profile.

n	$\alpha_{n,0}$	n	$\alpha_{n,0}$
0	0.838955	7	0.0542893
1	0.226465	8	-0.0282217
2	-0.29083	9	-0.0191844
3	0.144941	10	-0.0325897
4	0.0451785	11	0.0629701
5	-0.12261	12	-0.0162824
6	0.0363047		

In longitudinal direction, the laser is idealized for this simulation campaign. In reality there are always some dispersive effects present, which are all neglected here. The laser is linear polarized in x-direction and propagates in z-direction. All these parameters are kept constant for the whole optimization campaign. The parameters, which were optimized, are the beam waist w_0 , the focus position z_{foc} and the dimensionless field strength parameter a_0 . These parameters are known to have a strong impact on the acceleration process. A range of permitted values was defined for each of these parameters. The three parameter ranges thus span the parameter space in which the optimal configuration that reconstructs the target spectrum is to be found. The ranges are given in table 4.2. The range are set in a way that they represent the uncertainties around the set parameter values in the experiment.

Table 4.2: Ranges of the parameters for the Bayesian optimization. The limits for the focus position were increased after 19 simulations, because the optimization lead to parameters on the lower limit.

	lower bound	upper bound
w_0	20 μm	24 μm
z_{foc}	1.2 mm (0.8 mm)	1.9 mm (2.5 mm)
a_0	1.8	2.45

With the parameters in the set ranges in table 4.2, ten start parameter points were defined and simulations were carried out. Based on the output of the initial simulations, the optimization was performed for several iterations. After a total of 30 simulations, the objective did not decrease further. The smallest objective was attained after 25 simulations, including the 10 initial ones. It has a value of 6439 and was obtained with a beam waist $w_0 = 20.4056 \mu\text{m}$, the focus position at $z_{\text{foc}} = 1.0624 \text{ mm}$ and a laser field strength of $a_0 = 2.1058$. An overview about the performance of the simulations can be seen in figure 4.4. There each simulation is represented as one point in each subplot, the color of the point corresponds to the objective. Each subplot shows another distribution of the objective function between the varied laser parameters. It can be seen that a clustering of simulations happened close to the optimum. In fact, the optimization algorithm found this region very quickly. The first simulation with an objective smaller than 7000 was reached at simulation 13, including the 10 initial simulations, even though the average objective of the randomly sampled initial parameters was 11043.

The electron spectrometer for the minimal objective can be seen in figure 4.5. For better comparison, the projections of the target spectrometer and the simulated spectra on the energy and deflection angle are depicted. At first glance, the energy distribution agreement looks promis-

Figure 4.4: Overview about the performed simulations of the Initial optimization run. The color of the points corresponds to the objective as defined in section 4.2.2.

ing. The energy spread defined as the full width at half maximum (FWHM) is 39.29 MeV for the simulated spectra and 43.29 MeV for the target spectra. This corresponds to a deviation of 10.2 % between the simulation and the target. The total charge of the electron bunch, considering every electron which reached an energy of 100 MeV agrees also quite well. The absolute values for the energy also agree to a good extent as visible in figure 4.5. The target total energy is 443.06 pC and the charge of the simulation is 472.49 pC, which corresponds to a relative deviation of 6.2 %, which is a satisfactory agreement. The agreement of the divergence is less satisfying. There the standard deviation of a Gaussian fit of the projection of the deflection angle is compared between the target spectrum and the simulated spectrum. The target standard deviation is 1.92 mrad, but the simulated spectrum has a standard deviation of θ of 4.49 mrad, which is more than twice the anticipated divergence.

There could be multiple reasons for the high deviation between the target and simulation divergence. The origin could be in the configuration of the optimization, especially the definition of the objective is very sensitive to the optimization result. To test this, 6 further simulations were performed, where the Bayesian optimization was used with the divergence as an objective. This did not lead to an improvement of the divergence or the former defined objective. This indicates that there is no point in the parameter space under consideration that leads to a reasonably small divergence. In order to reduce the divergence, various modifications of the initial simulation setup were investigated. Their impact is shown in the next section.

4.3.2 Adjustments for experimental agreement

The initial setup already led to satisfactory results in modeling the energy distribution of an experimental electron bunch. However, the divergence was overestimated for each point in the parameter space. In order to find a setup that can reproduce the experimental divergence, the effect of different physical parameters on the divergence was investigated. The parameters in question are the transversal laser shape, the shape of the plasma density profile, and the choice of the field solver, which is critical for numerical stability and can lead to the appearance of non-physical radiation that can cause changes in the simulation output. The goal was to find a

Figure 4.5: Final electron spectrum of the optimization. The projection of the energy and divergence (orange) are compared with the projections of the target spectrometer (gray).

setup that can be successfully optimized to the experimental setup. For this purpose, an attempt was made to reduce the required resources per simulation. The results of these modifications are described below.

Laguerre modes

The used laser profile considers 13 radial Laguerre laser modes. Their contribution to the transversal laser profile is given in table 4.1. The impact of Laguerre modes on laser electron acceleration is complex and not yet fully described [47]. It is therefore unclear if they have an impact on the electron spectrum and the divergence in particular. Including Laguerre modes as variable parameters for the optimization is not ideal, as this would require up to 13 new dimensions to be optimized, which would require many more simulations and make the optimization significantly more difficult.

To investigate the impact of the single modes, 8 further simulations were carried out. For each simulation, the number of Laguerre modes considered was decreased by one, starting with the previously found optimal setup and continuing by neglecting the 12th-order mode, then the 11th-order mode, and so on. The resulting electron spectra can be seen in figure 4.6

It can be seen in figure 4.6 that the mode composition changes the outcome in the electron spectrometer in a non-systematic way. Even the higher modes, with a comparatively small contribution to the overall transversal laser profile, appear to have a non-negligible effect on the accelerated charge. It was expected that the impact of the higher order modes due to their low contribution is not significant. By neglecting laser modes, the total laser energy changes, which might lead to the difference in the reached bunch energy. To test this theory, three simulations were run again with an adapted laser strength a_0 to match the total laser energy of the simulations considering all initial modes. The resulting electron spectra can be seen in figure 4.7. The energies are as expected more equally in the energy adapted case than before. However, the overall appearance of the electron spectra is conserved, meaning that the energy spread, divergence and maximum values of the partial charge distribution $d^2Q/dE d\theta$ remain similar. The impact of the Laguerre modes on the divergence is insignificant.

Overall, the effect of Laguerre modes is ambiguous and difficult to interpret. As mentioned above, it is impractical to consider Laguerre modes for optimization because they lead to too many degrees of freedom. Also, since the impact on divergence is so small, it seems unreasonable

Figure 4.6: Impact of Laguerre modes on the electron spectra. *Mode 0 - x* considers all radial Laguerre modes with $n \leq x$ and sets all higher modes to 0.

to investigate the influences of the modes on the divergence further. It was decided to neglect the Laguerre modes in the further optimization process and to assume a Gaussian transversal laser profile. This simplification allows to investigate the influence of laser dispersion in PIConGPU.

Figure 4.7: Impact of Laguerre modes with adapted Laser energy. The laser field strength was adapted in a way that all simulations have the same total laser energy. *Mode 0 - x* considers all radial Laguerre modes with $n \leq x$ and sets all higher modes to 0.

Down-ramp of density profile

The moment in which the electron bunch leaves the plasma can have a significant impact on the divergence of the electron bunch. The electron bunch is focused and defocused during the acceleration in the plasma bubble and electrons oscillate around the laser axis. Therefore, the electrons experience betatron oscillations and rotate in transversal phase space. Due to energy differences, this leads to a completely filled phase space, called betatron decoherence [48]. A filled transverse phase space occurs quickly if the electron bunch is comparably long and has an energy chirp. Then the phase difference of the electrons at different longitudinal positions is high enough that there are always focused and defocused electrons in the bunch. If the phase space is not completely filled, the moment of extraction from the plasma matters. The electrons can be

extracted when the transversal momentum is currently high and the transversal spread is low or the other way around. If they are extracted while the transversal spread is low, the divergence can be reduced [48].

Figure 4.8: Alteration of the downramp of the density profile. The downramp is modeled by a Gaussian function with a standard deviation of σ_{DR} . The dark blue cases corresponds to the initially used density profile.

In discussion with the experimentalist it became known that the exact density profile of the plasma is not known and therefore minor alterations are possible while staying true to the experimental setup. In order to investigate if the phase space is not filled and the divergence depends on the moment of extraction, 4 different plasma density downramps were modeled. The different downramps can be seen in figure 4.8. The downramp was modeled by a Gaussian function and the standard deviation of it was altered to create shallower ramps and therefore longer plasma profiles.

The impact of the different density downramps can be seen in figure 4.9. The divergence is in fact decreasing with a shallower slope indicating that the phase space is not fully filled and the position of the coupling out of the focusing field seems to have an impact on the electron divergence. The divergence was decreased to a value of 3.53 mrad. As a reminder, the target electron spectrum has a divergence of 1.93 mrad. This means that the impact is not neglectable, but also not sufficient in order to reach the experimental divergence. Since in figure 4.8 the trend of the divergence is decreasing, one might think that the divergence could be further reduced by extending the density ramp further and further. This is not the case, since the beam envelope oscillates and a phase with high transversal momentum will be reached again leading to a higher divergence. For a density downramp with $\sigma_{DR} = 1.0$ mrad the divergence of the electron beam is already increasing again, as can be seen in figure 4.9.

Background plasma

In 2023, a method to drastically reduce the divergence of a laser-plasma accelerated electron bunch was developed at HZDR by Chang et al. [49]. There, a wedge is placed into the gas flow, causing the plasma profile to extend several millimeters at a lower density. This low density plasma acts as a plasma lense and collimates the electron beam. Collimation occurs because in the lower density plasma the diverging laser beam can no longer drive a wake in the bubble regime. Thus, the cavity is not completely evacuated of electrons and the electron bunch starts driving its own wake. As the laser diverges further, a transition occurs from the laser-dominated regime through a mixed laser-driven and beam-driven regime to a fully beam-driven regime. The cavity created in the beam-driven regime has a focusing field that collimates the electron bunch [49].

Figure 4.9: Angular charge distribution depending on the slope of the plasma density downramp. The colors correspond to the colors in figure 4.8 and the values for σ_θ are determined by the standard deviation of a Gaussian fit of the charge distribution.

Such a wedge was not placed into the gas flow at the experiment which is supposed to be recreated in this simulation campaign and therefore no such plasma lens existed. Simulations and measurements of the gas density have shown that 1 to 2 mm beyond the previously expected density drop, a background plasma with a density two orders of magnitude lower could still be present. For the plasma lens effect in [49], the low-density region with a density two orders of magnitude lower than the plasma plateau was investigated, but for a much longer than 1 to 2 mm, but rather 6 to 8 mm.

Here, we want to investigate of the effect of the plasma lens in the first millimeter after the plasma density plateau. Therefore, the density profile is extended by about one millimeter with an additional density plateau with a density of $4 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which is one percent of the plateau density. The resulting plasma density profile is shown in figure 4.10.

Figure 4.10: Plasma density profile including background plasma. The green and red dashed line correspond to the spatial position where the divergence will be compared in figure 4.11b

For this plasma density profile, a simulation was carried out and the angular distribution for several time steps evaluated. The evolution of this distribution can be seen in figure 4.11a. The green and red lines correspond to the absolute positions which are marked in figure 4.10. The angular charge distribution becomes increasingly narrower as the electron bunch propagates in the background plasma due to the plasma lens effect. The divergence at the end of the low density plateau is shown in figure 4.11b and significantly decreases to 2.48 mrad.

This significant decrease could solve the previously discussed problem of reconstructing the

(a) Evolution of the angular charge distribution in the background plasma. (b) Divergence before and at the end of the background plasma.

Figure 4.11: Impact on the angular charge distribution and the divergence of the background plasma plateau. The green and red line in figure 4.11a correspond to the green and red charge distribution in subfigure 4.11b. The solid green and red line in 4.11b correspond to a Gaussian fit of the distribution. The gray angular distribution in 4.11b corresponds to the target histogram.

low divergence. The interaction of the electron bunch with the background plasma also affects other properties of the electron bunch. To get a rough estimate of the effect on the energy of the electron bunch, the evolution of the energy over the propagation is shown in figure 4.12. It can be seen that the energy is continuously decreasing till the end of the simulation duration. The energy spread also decrease slightly. This means, that for the recreation of the experimental results it is insufficient to just prolong the plasma profile and reach agreement with the target spectrum, because in this case the divergence would be better represented, but the energy properties of the electron bunch would alter in an unintended way. It is rather necessary to adapt the simulation setup and optimize again for the target spectrum. This will be further discussed in section 4.3.3.

Technical Adaptations: Field solvers

Another source for deviations from the experiment can originate from numerical instabilities and errors. A common example is the choice of the field solver and the resolution of the grid and the time step. The field solver is responsible for solving the Maxwell equations on the simulation grid and therefore for the calculation of the electromagnetic fields. It is evident that discretizing the calculation of the fields results in the introduction of numerical errors. These numerical errors can cause numerical radiation, which can apply a force to the accelerated electrons and therefore alter their pointing and consequently their divergence. It is possible to reduce, though not eliminate, the impact of these alterations by increasing the resolution of the simulation. This can be achieved by reducing the distance between two neighboring grid points and the duration of a time step.

In PIconGPU four different field solvers are implemented. These are the Yee, Lehe, Cole-Karkkainen-Cowan (CKC) and the arbitrary order finite-difference time domain (AOFDTD) solver. The latter solver is neglected in the following, as it requires too fine a resolution to be useful in this case. The Lehe solver was used for the initial parameter optimization scan.

To determine whether the choice of field solver changes the underlying physics, the previously

Figure 4.12: Impact of the plasma background plateau on the energy of the electron bunch. The green line corresponds to the position before the plateau occurs marked in figure 4.10.

determined laser parameters were simulated with the Yee and CKC solvers. The time and space resolution was adjusted according to the requirements of each solver. The electron spectrum of these simulations is compared to the initial simulation using the Lehe solver in figure 4.13. In fact, the choice of solver has a significant impact on the electron bunch. The energy, energy spread, divergence and the charge density varies between all three solvers. That the choice of field solver is that significant was unexpected.

Figure 4.13: Electron spectrometer showing the impact of the field solver on the accelerated electron bunch. For the upper plot the simulation was carried out with the Yee solver, in the middle with the Lehe solver and at the bottom with the CKC solver.

To investigate the reason for these differences of the electron spectrometer, the transversal component of the Lorentz force (focussing fields) $F_{\perp/q} \approx E_y + cB_x$ was calculated with the field components E_y and B_x of the electromagnetic field. Note that this definition assumes $v_z \approx c$ and $v_z \gg v_x$. The resulting fields are shown in figure 4.14 for an exemplary time step, where injection

already occurred.

Figure 4.14: Transverse field inside the first cavity. The contour of the electron distribution is shown in gray to visualize the electron bunch and the cavity. The subplots show the electron distribution and the transversal field for the same time step for the Yee, Lehe and CKC solvers from left to right.

In an ideal case there would be no perturbations to the transversal focussing fields. In reality there can be perturbations seen for each solver in figure 4.14. The effect present for the simulation using the Yee solver is known and is called numerical Cherenkov radiation [50, 51]. This occurs because the group velocity of an electromagnetic wave in vacuum is underestimated and therefore the velocity of the particles in the simulation can exceed the speed of light and cause Cherenkov radiation. The Lehe solver, on the other hand, overestimates the group velocity of the electromagnetic wave. This prevents numerical Cherenkov radiation, but there is another effect. Very high frequency radiation occurs in and behind the electron beam. The intensity is rather low compared to the radiation of the other solvers. This radiation is observed at the Nyquist frequency and was already investigated by Lehe [44]. The impact can reach unacceptable levels, but when choosing the right resolution, the impact is much smaller than the one of Cherenkov radiation. The CKC Solver is known to be dispersion free for vacuum propagation of electromagnetic waves. When modeling the interaction with charged particles, dispersion can occur. Godfrey and Vay [52] proposed to reduce the duration of one time step by a factor of two in order to reduce the radiation effect. This may reduce the radiation for the CKC solver in plasma, but halving the time step doubles the computational resources, which is not feasible for the optimization studies presented here.

For infinite fine resolution, the calculated fields of each field solver should converge. The question is for which solver the time step can be largest and the result obtained is still physical. For the time being, the Lehe solver seemed to cause the least amount of numerical radiation with a resolution that did not require an unfeasible amount of computational resources. To further improve the simulation output, a binomial filter to the current interpolation has been applied. The radiation of a simulation with the binomial filter in comparison to a simulation without a filter can be seen in figure 4.15. With the help of the filter, the oscillations at the Nyquist frequency can be reduced significantly. The impact on the divergence of the filter is neglectable.

4.3.3 Summary of adaptations and final simulation setup

In order to improve the optimization results from the initial setup in section 4.3.1, different possible adjustments were investigated and discussed in section 4.3.2. Now, the simulation setup was modified and the optimization is run again to improve the previously found objective.

The impact of the Laguerre modes is significant and sensitive to the exact mode composition. Studying the effect of the Laguerre mode composition would require a separate extensive simula-

Figure 4.15: Impact of a binomial filter on the transversal field. On the left the simulation without filter is shown and on the right with binomial filter.

tion study. In addition, they most likely will not reduce the divergence. It was decided here that it is of greater interest to study the temporal structure of the laser pulse and to neglect transversal modifications here.

The background plasma had the most promising effect on the divergence, so it was included in the simulation setup. Varying the slope and length of the plasma density gradient also seemed to have an interesting effect on the electron beam properties, and in order to study this systematically, the plasma profile was slightly modified. The up and downramp were modeled with a Gaussian function and the plateau was assumed to have a constant base density. The slope of the ramps was chosen to match the downramp of the initial density profile. After the downramp, a plateau with a density of approximately 1 % of the base density is added. As a field solver the Lehe solver was again used together with the binomial filter.

In the first optimization run, which considered 3 variable parameters, was able to find an optimum after very few simulations, in the second attempt of an optimization for 7 parameters was attempted. These parameters were again the laser field strength a_0 , the focus position z_{foc} and the beam waist w_0 . Additionally, the group delay dispersion GDD , the slope of the downramp of the plasma, the base density n_e of the plasma and the density of the background plasma were chosen as optimization parameters. Because the parameter space is much bigger, 20 initial simulations were performed. These were sampled again with LHS. A total of 34 simulations were run. Many of them did not lead to electron injection, causing the definition objective to fail, since the objective for no injection at all is comparatively good, as discussed in 4.2.2. This leads the optimization algorithm to optimize for no injection. When this became obvious, the objective was weighted by the total amount of charge injected. After 34 simulations the objective did not converge and did not show a trend towards minimizing the objective. Overall, the optimization with 7 variable parameters proved to be more challenging and not feasible with the limited time and computational resources. To improve the experimental reconstruction, a smaller parameter space had to be chosen.

The number of optimization parameters has been reduced to 4, which are the beam waist w_0 , the focus position z_{foc} , the field strength parameter a_0 and the base density n_e . The ranges for this optimization campaign are declared in table 4.3.

The range for the focus position has been slightly shifted to higher values than in the first optimization campaign (see Table 4.2) because the newly defined plasma profile is also slightly shifted. The range of the focus position for both optimization campaigns is equivalent with respect to the start of the base density plateau. The density of the background plasma was set to

Table 4.3: Ranges of the parameters for the final Bayesian optimization run.

	lower bound	upper bound
w_0	20 μm	24 μm
z_{foc}	1.2 mm	2.4 mm
a_0	1.8	2.45
n_e	$3.3 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$	$3.3 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$

$3.5 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which is about 1 % of the base density. In agreement with the experimentalists, the proportion of nitrogen in the plasma was reduced from 4 % to 3 %, which is more realistic.

Again, 14 initial parameters in the parameter space were generated using LHS. With this physical setup and these optimization conditions, the final optimization run was performed.

4.4 Evaluation and interpretation of optimization outcomes

Reproducing simulations using the Bayesian algorithm requires a fundamental understanding of the parameter space of interest and the physical setup to be modeled. Here, several adjustments had to be made in order to reproduce the experimental electron spectrum. Their impact and the extent to which the approach chosen here to reproduce an experiment was successful will be discussed in this section. In addition, the difficulties and possibilities of using Bayesian optimization to achieve good agreement between experiment and simulation are briefly summarized.

Final results of Bayesian optimization

For the final optimization campaign, in total 30 simulations were performed. The resulting distribution of their objective values can be seen in figure 4.16. It can be seen that clustering occurred at the edge of the parameter space where the optimum was found.

Figure 4.16: Overview about the performed simulations of the final optimization run. The color of the points corresponds to the objective as defined in section 4.2.2.

With the last optimization campaign, a suitable reconstruction of the experimental electron spectrum was found. The electron spectrum closest to the target spectrum was reached after 27 simulations, including the initial ones. The electron spectrum of the closest simulation to the target spectrum can be seen in figure 4.17. This simulation was performed with a beam waist of $w_0 = 20.0 \mu\text{m}$, the focus position at $z_{\text{foc}} = 1.2 \text{ mm}$, a laser field strength of $a_0 = 2.3127$ and a base density of $n_e = 3.3 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The objective value reached in this run was 5150, which is significantly lower than the best objective of the first run of 6439. The main reason for this improvement is the more accurate reproduction of the divergence. The simulated divergence of the electron beam is now $\sigma_\theta = 2.2 \text{ mrad}$ compared to the target spectra with a divergence of $\sigma_\theta = 1.9 \text{ mrad}$, which is a massive improvement in comparison to the first optimization attempt, where the divergence was $\sigma_\theta = 4.3 \text{ mrad}$. This reduces the relative deviation from 55 % to 10 %. The main reason for this improvement is the introduction of the background plasma.

Figure 4.17: Final electron spectrum of the optimization. The projection of the energy and divergence (orange) are compared with the projections of the target spectrum (gray).

Unfortunately, the energy distribution for this optimization setup was not as well modeled as before. The FWHM width of the distribution is still off by 10.2 % as for the first optimization campaign, but there is now a new deviating feature present. The electron spectrum shows that some electrons reach higher energies than the target energy and form a high-energy tail. The appearance of this tail is not common in experiments. In this optimization campaign, the tail was there for almost every parameter point. This suggests that there are still deviations in the modeling of the experiment that favor this tail. One possible deviation is the transverse laser profile, which was neglected here, but was taken into account in the first optimization and where the electron distribution did not show this feature. The effect of several other parameters on this high-energy tail, as well as the reason for its appearance, will be examined in detail in Chapter 5.

Overall, the agreement between the now found optimal electron spectrum and the experimental spectrum is sufficient to continue. The energy and the divergence are modelled according to the target spectra. Fluctuation of the beam properties are also present in the experiment and therefore also tolerable.

Advantages of using Bayesian optimization to reproduce experiments through simulation

The Bayesian optimization shows promising results for the recreation of experimental results. The method is based on several hyperparameters, most of which were left at default values for this campaign. Even with this non-optimized optimization setup, good results were achieved.

It is certainly of interest how the optimization could be accelerated or stabilized with adjusted hyperparameters. The only difficulty here is that optimizing hyperparameters also consumes computing resources, but does not provide any gain in information regarding the physics. This disadvantage must be weighed against possible advantages of finding an optimum quicker.

Another difficult issue is the choice of parameter sets and their ranges. Choosing ranges that are too wide makes the optimization unnecessarily difficult and may increase the number of simulations needed to find an optimum. Decreasing the parameter ranges requires neglecting all simulations previously performed outside the narrower parameter setting. Choosing ranges that are too narrow may result in a case similar to the one just presented, namely an optimum at the edge of the parameter space. This is not ideal, since the true optimum is most likely outside the parameter ranges. Enlarging the parameter ranges in the middle of the optimization campaign is possible, but carries two risks. First, the surrogate model may struggle to make reasonable predictions in the region where there are no samples yet. Second, if the acquisition function is too exploitative and not explorative, the additional space in the parameter space may not be taken into account.

For 3 to 4 variable input parameters, the objective was converging very quickly. In the second optimization run, the limits of the method in adaptation with large scale simulations were tested. Optimizing for 7 input parameters does not seem feasible with the limited amount of computational resources available. In addition, it was found that the definition of the objective is not ideal for large parameter spaces and leads to incorrect behavior in the absence of injection.

A huge advantage of the optimization workflow is that adapting it to various use cases is very easy. One can easily adapt the target spectrum and optimize for other electron beam parameters. With the implemented workflow the alteration of different laser or plasma parameters is straight forward. Additionally, the Bayesian optimization can be used with multiple different objective functions and therefore is not at all limited to recreation of experimental values, as shown previously in [37, 36].

The Bayesian optimization proved to be an easy-to-use, efficient method for recreating experimental results and demonstrated its capability to quickly converge toward an optimum for several parameters. Even with minimal tuning of the hyperparameters, the method delivered reliable results, showcasing its robustness. Its substantial flexibility makes it well-suited for a variety of use cases beyond its initial implementation.

Conclusion

Overall, Bayesian optimization is a useful tool to reproduce the experimental properties of the LWFA electron beam in the simulation. For 4 variable parameters, the number of simulations required is manageable, and with the number of initial parameters used, an optimum could be found quickly. The consideration of a background plasma is a fundamental finding in this optimization study and allows reproducing realistically low divergences in simulations, which has always been challenging. The simulation setup found here reproduces the experimental electron beam properties close enough to allow to start the investigation of the sensitivities of the electron beam properties, as will be done in chapter 5.

5 Sensitivity analysis of Laser electron acceleration

Laser plasma acceleration processes are subject to several non-linear effects, and it is not uncommon for small changes in the experimental setup to result in large differences in the accelerated electron bunch properties. Control of the electron beam properties is crucial for several reasons. For example, if the bunch is to be used for an FEL, it is important to have a low energy spread and divergence and a high injected charge in order to generate the expected FEL light. Which laser or plasma parameters have the greatest influence on the above-mentioned bunch parameters remains to a large extent unknown. With the previously found simulation setup, which resembles a realistic experiment, the sensitivity of the electron bunch properties to laser or plasma parameters can be investigated. For this purpose, two different two-dimensional parameter spaces were sampled and the dependence of the electron bunch properties was investigated. This was done using multivariate polynomial interpolation, which is introduced and described in section 5.1.1. The results and findings of the interpolation are presented and discussed in sections 5.2 to 5.4.

5.1 Defining dependencies in a multi-parameter space

5.1.1 Multivariate polynomial interpolation

Interpolation is a common technique, which allows the visualization of dependencies as well as creating a model of dependencies. Polynomials of degree n are functions of the form

$$p(x) = a_0 + a_1x + \dots + a_nx^n \mid a_i \in \mathbb{R}, i = 0, \dots, n \quad (5.1)$$

and are frequently used to model dependencies. This is due to the fact that each function $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ on a compact set Ω can be uniformly approximated by a polynomial as proven by the Weierstrass approximation theorem [53]. Furthermore, polynomial evaluations are straightforward, allowing model properties to be extracted easily. It will therefore be used to visualize the dependencies of the parameter scans performed in section 5.2 and 5.3. A brief introduction to the pitfalls of multivariate interpolation and how it was performed is given in this section.

In one dimension, a function with $n+1$ uniquely solvable interpolation points is uniquely represented by a polynomial of degree n . This is the significant difference from approximation, where the overall deviation may be smaller, but given points may not be accurately represented by the fitted function. Even though this unique solution exists, it is not guaranteed that the deviation

between the function $f(x)$ and its polynomial representation $p(x)$ will be small. It is evident that the error does not necessarily diminish for a higher polynomial degree [54]. The reason for that is the so called Runge phenomenon or Runge oscillations, a case of overfitting [55]. Since polynomials tend to $\pm\infty$ for $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$, they fail to represent functions which behave differently, like converging or periodic functions. If the polynomial degree is too high, oscillations will occur at the edge of the interpolation interval, making polynomial interpolation over the entire interval impractical. In order to minimize the occurrence of this error, it is essential to select interpolation points which minimizes the error $f(x) - p(x)$.

To achieve this, the open source Python module MinterPy was used to define sampling points in the parameter space. It uses Chebyshev extreme nodes for sampling, which are defined for one dimension and polynomial degree n on an interval of $[-1, 1]$ as

$$P = \{x_0, \dots, x_n\} = \left\{ \cos \left(\frac{k\pi}{n} \right) \mid 0 \leq k \leq n \right\}. \quad (5.2)$$

This particular choice of interpolation nodes results in closer sampling towards the edge of the interpolation interval rather than equidistant sampling, which suppresses Runge's phenomenon. To extend the parameter set to m dimensions, select a subset of all possible combinations of parameter m -tuples. This subset does not necessarily have to be tensorial, and therefore the number of interpolation nodes scales sub-exponentially with the dimension [54].

For the specific use case of investigating the sensitivity of laser and plasma parameters on the electron bunch, it was considered feasible to have 7 sampling points in each dimension. The optimum found in chapter 4 is chosen as the center of the investigated parameter space, causing the need for an even polynomial degree and therefore odd number of interpolation nodes. The decision of how many interpolation nodes are reasonable is hard to predict in advance. Considering that each simulation requires an immense amount of computing resources, the number of simulations was kept to a minimum. Having the same reason in mind, one has to think about the dimension. It is possible to investigate m -dimensional dependencies with polynomial interpolation, but even though MinterPy creates interpolation nodes on a non-tensorial grid, meaning the number of nodes grows subexponential with the number of dimensions, 2 dimensions with a polynomial of 6th degree already requires 35 simulations, 3 dimensions require 163, which is not feasible with the available compute resources and time. In order to obtain the optimal ratio between the resources required and the information obtained, it was decided to investigate two separate two-dimensional parameter spaces, for each of which 35 simulations were performed. The simulations were performed and the electron beam parameters were calculated for each interpolation node.

The actual polynomial interpolation was performed utilizing MinterPy which solved the interpolation using the Lagrange formalism and transformed it into Newton basis afterwards.

Each polynomial is defined as an element of the polynomial space which is a vector space. There are several algorithms to solve the interpolation for different bases of the polynomial space. For simplicity, a brief overview about some one-dimensional polynomial bases is given here as well as an overview about how the interpolation was carried out. The canonical or monomial basis is the best-known example of a polynomial basis and is given by

$$\mathfrak{B}_{\text{canonical}} = \{1, x, x^1, \dots, x^n\} \quad (5.3)$$

and defines a polynomial of the same form as in equation 5.1. Interpolation in the canonical basis is computational expensive and leads to numerical instabilities for values much smaller or larger than 0, especially for a high polynomial degree [54]. Evaluation in the Lagrange basis

are computational less expensive and are therefor preferred by MinterPy. The Lagrange basis is defined by the Lagrange polynomials:

$$\mathfrak{B}_{\text{Lagrange}} = \{l_0, l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n\}, \quad (5.4)$$

$$l_i(x_k) = \prod_{\substack{0 \leq j \leq n \\ j \neq i}} \frac{x_k - x_j}{x_i - x_j} = \delta_{ik} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = k \\ 0 & \text{if } i \neq k \end{cases} \quad (5.5)$$

where $x_j, x_k \in P = \{x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n\}$. For the corresponding evaluated values $\{f_0, f_1, \dots, f_n\}$ the polynomial in Lagrange basis can be written as

$$L(x) = \sum_{j=0}^n f_j \cdot l_j(x). \quad (5.6)$$

Solving the interpolation in Lagrange basis is independent of the function values. Therefore, different interpolations on the same interpolation nodes can be solved easily once the basis polynomials are determined. Another basis is called the Newton basis, which is defined as

$$\mathfrak{B}_{\text{Newton}} = \{m_0, \dots, m_n\} \quad (5.7)$$

$$m_0(x) = 1 \quad (5.8)$$

$$m_i(x) = \prod_{j=0}^{i-1} (x - x_j). \quad (5.9)$$

The Newton polynomials are given by

$$N(x) = \sum_{j=0}^n a_j m_j(x), \quad m_j \in \mathfrak{B}_{\text{Newton}}, \quad a_j \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (5.10)$$

In particular, Newton polynomials are numerically stable and very accurate to evaluate, making this the preferred basis for polynomial evaluation. In MinterPy, the transformation into the Newton basis is efficiently implemented and was performed on the Lagrange polynomial. The transformation requires a matrix multiplication of the Lagrange basis to obtain the corresponding Newton basis. The details can be found in [56].

For the multivariate interpolation, each interpolation node is m-dimensional and one needs to define a multi-index set $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}^m$, which generalizes the polynomial degree to multiple dimensions. For each element of A , a polynomial is determined, and their superposition gives the result of the multivariate interpolation. To solve the multivariate interpolation, the definition of the polynomial bases is slightly different, as described in [54], but the general algorithm remains similar.

5.1.2 Definition and evaluation of bunch properties

As mentioned before, the multivariate polynomial interpolation maps a set of input parameters, in this case a two-dimensional parameter space, onto a scalar value. The need arises to define one dimensional properties to characterize the electron bunch, about which we want to gain information. The objective, which was defined in section 4.2.2 is not sufficient, because it combines several properties into one scalar, which does not allow any conclusions to be drawn about the individual electron beam properties. However, since the results of the interpolation are also to be used for recommendations to the experimentalist, it is advantageous to use properties that

Figure 5.1: Definition of bunch properties: In 5.1a the energy projection of an exemplary electron spectrum is shown in magenta. The peak charge $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\max}$ and the corresponding energy E_{peak} are highlighted in dark orange and the width E_{spread} is labeled in blue. In 5.1b the divergence distribution for electrons, which are in the FWHM region of the energy distribution, is shown in magenta. The distribution is fitted by a Gauss function, visualized via a dotted golden line. As the comparable parameter the standard deviation σ_{θ} of the fit, highlighted in gold, is selected.

can be extracted from the electron spectrometer introduced in section 2.5. Additionally, electron beam properties which are relevant for operating an FEL are of particular relevance.

To obtain the relevant values, the projection of the electron spectrum to the energy dimension is calculated, resulting in the $\frac{dQ}{dE}$ distribution. An example for this is shown in figure 5.1a. The most interesting value is $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\max}$, which is defined as the maximum of the charge per energy distribution $\frac{dQ}{dE}$. The corresponding energy, where the charge reaches its maximum, is called E_{peak} . The energy width is defined at 10% of $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\max}$. This is used instead of a full width at half maximum (FWHM) definition to make sure the high energy tail, which was already mentioned and discussed in chapter 4, is always considered. The width was determined with the python package SciPy [57] which determines the relative height of the peak in consideration of the prominence of the peak. In simple terms, this means that the background that is not part of the peak is subtracted from the absolute height and the width is determined at 10% of the resulting height.

Another important property is the divergence, which was introduced in 2.5. For the definition of this property, only particles in the FWHM around the $\frac{dQ}{dE}$ maximum are considered. There, the projection of the electron spectrum to the dimension of the transversal deflection angle θ is calculated. The resulting charge over θ distribution $\frac{dQ}{d\theta}$ is approximated by a Gaussian function. The standard deviation of this distribution σ_{θ} is the scalar value that is used as the function output of the polynomial fit to later compare the divergence of different simulations with each other.

Additionally, the total charge of all electrons which reach an energy of 100 MeV or more is of interest and was investigated. For this the symbol Q_{total} will be used.

5.2 Investigation of GDD and focus position dependencies

5.2.1 Parameters

Group-delay-dispersion

The group-delay-dispersion (GDD), as described in section 2.2, is the second order laser dispersion. In experiments at the DRACO laser at HZDR, it was observed that the stability and quality of the electron beam parameters depends on the setting of the dispersion control device. This is used to precisely control the spectral phase of the laser. Additional beamline elements towards the

target may add further dispersion, which makes the exact spectral phase at the target not fully known. To understand the sensitivity of the LWFA process to GDD, the physical effects of group delay dispersion are investigated in this simulation study.

The experimental range for GDD, used in most LWFA experiments, varies between approximately -500 fs^2 to 500 fs^2 . As GDD broadens the laser in the longitudinal direction, it becomes necessary to elongate the simulation box, which results in a higher demand for computational resources. Due to these increased computational costs, a narrower range is chosen for the simulation scan. To achieve an optimal balance between precision and computational cost, a range from -300 fs^2 to 300 fs^2 was selected.

Focus position

Experimentally, the focus position is varied by a deformable mirror, which currently allows only for discrete modifications of approximately 0.5 mm in z_{foc} . The vacuum focus position, in conjunction with the self-focusing effect, affects the intensity of the laser beam within the plasma, consequently influencing the electron injection into the plasma cavity. Considering, that the plasma profile itself has only a length of about 4 mm, 0.5 mm precision seem insufficient to control the resulting electron beam properties. To gain an understanding which precision would be beneficial, the focus position is another suitable candidate for the parameter scan.

The setup which matches the experiment best was determined in chapter 4 with $z_{\text{foc}} = 1.2 \text{ mm}$. In order to cover a range of approximately three potential experimental focus position settings, and in consideration of the fact that focusing before the plasma density profile carries the risk of prior defocusing, which would result in the absence of injection, the range for z_{foc} is selected to be between 0.5 mm to 1.9 mm.

5.2.2 Dependencies

As introduced in 5.1.1, the choice of sampling points is crucial to obtain a polynomial interpolation that accurately reflects the underlying dependencies. Therefore, the interpolation nodes were defined using MinterPy. A simulation is set up for each of the interpolation nodes. The general simulation setup is the same as described in 4.3.3, with the exception that a_0 , w_0 and the base density n_e are kept constant at the optimal values determined before. The simulations are performed with the help of Snakemake, which takes the parameters for GDD and z_{foc} , calculated by MinterPy, and compiles and runs the required 35 simulations automatically. After the simulations ran, the beam parameters, defined in section 5.1.2, are calculated for each simulation. For each of the beam parameters, an interpolation has been performed and will be shown and discussed in the following.

Peak height $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$

The most prominent parameter of the electron bunch is $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$, since it is crucial for the application in an FEL. In figure 5.2, the interpolation result for this parameter is visualized. The input parameters GDD and z_{foc} are depicted on the horizontal and vertical axis. The performed simulations are indicated by black-framed circles and are filled with the color corresponding to the actual value of $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$ for the specific electron bunch of the given simulation. The colormap in the background visualizes the polynomial of 6th degree, which interpolates the simulation results.

For GDD values ranging from approximately -200 fs^2 to 200 fs^2 and z_{foc} around 1.2 mm, the peak charge density $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$ is relatively stable in a high regime of about 8 pC MeV^{-1} to 9 pC MeV^{-1} . Towards absolute GDD values closer to 300 fs^2 , $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$ drops drastically, indicating a high degree

Figure 5.2: $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\max}$ dependency on GDD and z_{foc} : The black-framed circles represent the interpolation points, and their fill color indicates the actual value of $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\max}$ of the corresponding simulation. The colormap represents the interpolation result. The red dots correspond to the maximal and minimal value of the interpolation in the set parameter range.

of sensitivity to GDD within this range. For experimental applications, this means that keeping GDD values close to 0 fs^2 can be beneficial for stable electron beam properties.

Taking additionally the dependency on z_{foc} into account, the dependencies get more complex. The results indicate that there exists a stable island for z_{foc} approximately between 1.0 mm to 1.4 mm. However, for variations outside this stable section, there appears to be dependencies correlated with both input parameters, resulting in a cross-shaped interpolation structure. To understand these complex dependencies, it is useful to examine other electron beam properties that may be related to peak height, such as energy spread and total charge.

Energy spread E_{spread}

One of the most prominent alterations of the found optimum to the target spectra is the high energy spread towards higher energies. This high energy tail contains, compared to the main peak, little charge and occurs for almost every parameter set. The experimental result, which was supposed to be recreated, did not show this prominent feature. This suggests that the actual experimental configuration may lie beyond the specified parameter space investigated in chapter 4. One of the parameters that could affect this high energy tail and was not considered in the optimization is the group-delay-dispersion.

To investigate the effect of GDD , the polynomial interpolation of the energy spread E_{spread} depending on GDD and z_{foc} is shown in figure 5.3. There, a significant impact of the GDD on the occurrence of these high-energy electrons and consequently the energy spread is indicated. In most cases a small energy spread is favorable, which can be achieved for GDD values toward the edge of the investigated range, as can be seen in figure 5.3.

The energy spread should depend on the longitudinal length of the electron bunch, because if

Figure 5.3: E_{spread} dependency on GDD and z_{foc} . The black circles showcase the sampled parameters, their filling color corresponds to the E_{spread} value at this point. The colormap visualizes the interpolation result.

beam loading effects are neglected, the electron bunch experiences an inhomogeneous accelerating field, which is stronger at the back of the cavity and weaker towards its center. Theoretically, the energy spread for self-truncated ionization injection should be relatively narrow due to the limited injection duration and the resulting shorter electron bunch, as discussed in 2.4. The correlation between E_{spread} and the longitudinal length of the bunch z_{spread} was investigated and is illustrated in figure 5.4. In this context, z_{spread} corresponds to the width of the dQ/dz distribution at 10% of the maximum of said distribution. Exemplary, this is visualized in 5.5a. The Pearson correlation coefficient between the energy spread and the length of the electron bunch is 0.87, indicating that the two properties are indeed strongly related.

As mentioned before this correlation is plausible, since the electron bunch experiences an inhomogeneous accelerating field inside the cavity. But with this explanation, it remains unclear why the energy distribution is so uneven and why these high-energy outliers appear. Further investigations considered the spatial charge distribution for two different GDD values. This is illustrated on the left side of the figure 5.5, where it can be seen that this spatial charge distribution has two maxima. To investigate how this spatial charge distribution corresponds to the energy distribution, the electrons in the two peaks were separately investigated. The separation is illustrated in figure 5.5. There, the electrons closer to the front of the cavity are colored in orange and the electrons further back in the cavity are colored in blue. For each of these cases, the charge per energy distribution $\frac{dQ}{dE}$ was generated separately and is shown on the right side of the figure 5.5. There, the orange histogram corresponds to the orange part of the spatial distribution and the blue histogram to the blue part of the spatial charge distribution. On the right side of figure 5.5a, it can be seen that the electrons further in the back of the cavity, depicted in blue, result in the high-energy outliers, at least for low GDD values. The one in the front, marked in orange, form the prominent energy peak.

So there are two spatially separated electron bunches, one responsible for the high charge peak in the $(d^2Q/dEdz)$ distribution and the other one for the high energy outliers. This raises two

Figure 5.5: Visualization of the longitudinal charge distribution on the left and the energy histogram on the right of the electron bunch is visualized. Subfigure 5.5a corresponds to a simulation with $GDD = 0 \text{ fs}^2$ and in 5.5b with $GDD = 300 \text{ fs}^2$. Additionally, in 5.5a the definition of z_{spread} is shown. On the left side, the spatial charge distribution for these two simulations are plotted. The part colored in blue corresponds to charge located in the rear part of the electron bunch and orange to particles in the front. On the right side the energy histogram is shown. For $GDD = 0 \text{ fs}^2$ in 5.5a it can be seen that the electrons with the highest energy, colored in blue, originate from the rear of the bunch, while in 5.5b the electrons from the rear of the cavity (also in blue) do not reach such high energies.

Figure 5.6: Origin of the double peak shape of the electron bunch. For two different time steps the trapping potential Ψ according to equation 2.13, is plotted in dark green. The area, where the trapping condition $\Delta\Psi \leq -1$ is fulfilled, is highlighted in green. The position where the laser is intense enough to ionize the $N^{5^+ \rightarrow 6^+}$ state or the $N^{6^+ \rightarrow 7^+}$ is marked with a green or orange dotted line respectively. The normalized laser amplitude is plotted in red. In the upper plot the bubble regime is not reached yet, but injection already occurred, visible by the density of the electrons from ionized nitrogen marked in gray. The injection also originates partially by the ionization $N^{5^+ \rightarrow 6^+}$ in earlier time steps and the injected charge hinders the bubble to fully close in the back. Between the two plotted time steps, the injection stops due to the laser focusing and the resulting forward shift of the point where the ionization energies are reached. In the plot at the bottom, the trapping condition is again fulfilled, because the bubble regime is reached and the final trapping potential Ψ_f decreases due to the much higher electron density (light blue) at the end of the bubble, which is now formed and the corresponding increased accelerating field causes the trapping condition to be fulfilled further downstream. The configuration in the upper plot causes the electrons in the front of the bubble and the configuration in the lower plot causes the electrons in the back of the bubble.

away from the cavity center, as can be seen in the lower plot of figure 5.6. Due to this effect, the ionized electrons can be captured again for a brief moment before, due to beam loading effects, the accelerating fields gets weakened further. These electrons correspond to the blue colored area in figure 5.5.

All of this is happening independently of the GDD value. The difference arises from the cavity formation, which differs due to the difference in laser intensity. For $GDD = 300 \text{ fs}^2$, the cavity is slightly smaller, because there is no laser induced wake elongation compared to $GDD = 0 \text{ fs}^2$. This leads to less charge separation and therefore smaller accelerating fields. The weakening of the wake is enough to lead to a non neglectable elongation of the cavity once charge is injected, even though the total charge is less in the $GDD = 300 \text{ fs}^2$ case. The elongation is that severe, that the wake is almost completely destroyed in the back. In figure 5.7 this is illustrated for two simulations, on the left side for $GDD = 0 \text{ fs}^2$ and for $GDD = 300 \text{ fs}^2$ on the right. The laser intensity is visualized in red, which is smaller for higher GDD. On the right side, the destruction of the wake is clearly visible. Consequently, the accelerating field, visualized in green, is weaker at the rear of the bunch, compared to the left plot, while in the front of the bunch the field is almost equal. This results in the electrons at the rear of the cavity not experiencing a stronger field, and thus not overtaking the electrons at the front in terms of energy. In contrast, in the $GDD = 0 \text{ fs}^2$ case, the cavity is not demolished, and the rear electrons experience a stronger accelerating field, reaching a point at which their energy surpasses that of the initially injected electrons.

Figure 5.7: Stability of the cavity for different GDD values: On the left a simulation with $GDD = 0 \text{ fs}^2$ and on the right with $GDD = 300 \text{ fs}^2$. The electron density for a slice in the center of the x -direction is plotted in blue, demonstrating the cavity and the electron bunch. The green graph corresponds to the accelerating field, while the red graph displays the laser intensity in units of a_0 .

Energy peak position E_{peak}

The energy peak position primarily depends on the focus position z_{foc} . This outcome was anticipated, as the focus position defines the point at which the laser reaches intensities sufficient to inject into the cavity. Consequently, it was expected that an earlier focus position would result in an increased electron energy, as an earlier injection allows the bunch to experience the accelerating field for a longer duration, thereby enabling it to reach higher energies. As illustrated in figure 5.8 this phenomenon is exclusive to simulations where $z_{\text{foc}} \geq 1.4 \text{ mm}$.

To understand this unexpected behavior, the injection position z_{inj} was investigated. For this purpose, the PICongPU energy histogram plugin was used. With the help of the plugin, the $\frac{dQ}{dE}$ distribution for every 50th time step was stored. In this histogram, the maximum value for $\frac{dQ}{dE}$ was determined for the horizontal energy bins. These maxima are visualized in pink in figure 5.9 and

Figure 5.8: E_{peak} dependency on GDD and z_{foc} . The black circles showcase the sampled parameters, their filling color corresponds to the E_{peak} value at this point. The colormap visualizes the interpolation result.

Figure 5.9: Determination of the injection position z_{inj} . The histogram shows the energy evolution of the simulations. The position of the maximum was determined for the horizontal energy bins and is indicated by the pink dotted line. The maximum values between 20 MeV and 35 MeV were approximated with a linear function, which is marked in dark red. The intersection of the approximation with the abscissa axis defines injection point z_{inj} .

are approximated with a linear function. The intersection of the linear function with the z-axis is considered as the injection position z_{inj} . This method of determining the injection position has some uncertainty because the injection occurs over a longer period of time and the charge peak is not always as prominent. Here only z_{inj} as defined before is considered, but the following results can be taken as tendencies.

The relationship between z_{inj} and z_{foc} , illustrated on the left-hand side of figure 5.10a, does not align with the initial assumption that z_{inj} will increase in conjunction with z_{foc} . In the case of z_{foc} values below 1.2 mm, a decrease in injection position is observed as z_{foc} increases. This is due to the fact that for early focus positions, the laser reaches the focus before the plasma has reached a sufficient density for self-focusing effects to become significant. This effect can be observed in figure 5.10b, which depicts the evolution of the maximum value for a_0 in two simulations: one with $z_{foc} = 1.2$ mm and one with $z_{foc} = 0.59$ mm. The laser with $z_{foc} = 0.59$ mm has initially a higher intensity. But since it reaches its focus position before the plasma is dense enough for the self focusing effect to become significant, it stays at approximately the same intensity till self focusing becomes strong at about 1 mm. Till then, the natural defocusing and the slight plasma focussing cancel each other out. Meanwhile, the laser with $z_{foc} = 1.2$ mm gets constantly focussed as the plasma focussing effect increases, and consequently it surpasses the intensity of the earlier focussed laser.

Shortly thereafter, self-focusing effects become significant, and in both cases the intensity increases drastically. In conclusion, if the laser is focused before plasma self-focusing becomes relevant, the position where the maximum laser intensity is reached is shifted to later positions than for lasers focused after plasma self-focusing becomes relevant. As a result, the later focused laser leads to an earlier onset of ionization. If ionization starts earlier, the accelerating forces can act on the electron bunch for a longer time and it can reach higher energies. This can be seen on the right-hand side of figure 5.10a, where correlation between z_{inj} and E_{peak} is illustrated. This implies that an earlier injection in fact results in a higher energy.

Since the peak energy depends on the injection point and not on the focus position, it cannot be shifted to arbitrarily high values by just shifting the focus position to lower values. A maximum is reached when the laser is focussed at about 0.2 mm after the plasma reaches the base density. This is only a rough guide, as other parameters, such as the beam waist, can also affect the focusing behavior.

The dependencies of the peak energy on the focus position changes depicted in figure 5.8 show that the described behavior is present where the absolute value of GDD is small. For higher GDD values, the highest peak energy is reached for later focusing. This most likely is caused by the general lower peak laser intensity for dispersive lasers, which additionally alters the behavior during plasma propagation.

It was also investigated whether the different values for GDD have an impact on the resulting peak energy and respectively on the accelerating field. This was done by linear approximating the dependency of E_{peak} on z_{inj} for each GDD value separately, of which the slope should correspond to the average accelerating field experienced by the bunch. No significant correlation between the peak position E_{peak} and the group-delay-dispersion could be found.

Total charge

The total charge, highly dependence on the group delay dispersion, as depicted in figure 5.11a. One reason for this might be, that for higher absolute GDD values, the peak laser intensity decreases, and therefore the trapping condition are fulfilled for a shorter duration. This statement is supported by comparing the interpolation of Q_{total} with the length of the electron bunches z_{spread} , as shown in figure 5.11. Both properties rise with higher absolute values for GDD. Additionally, the highest total charge and the longest electron bunch occur for early focus positions.

(a) Injection position correlation to focus position and E_{peak} . The colors in both plots correspond to the GDD values.

(b) Evolution of laser intensity for focus positions of 0.59 and 1.2 mm.

Figure 5.10: Relationship between focus position and injection position.

(a) Q_{total} dependency on GDD and z_{foc} .

(b) z_{spread} dependency on GDD and z_{foc} .

Figure 5.11: Comparison of the dependencies of total charge Q_{total} and length of the electron bunch z_{spread} on the parameter space.

Divergence

The interpolation for the divergence in figure 5.12a demonstrates no correlation with the focus position z_{foc} , whereas the divergence for GDD exhibits a distinct change. With increasing GDD, the divergence rises in a parabolic manner. This can be explained by the lengthening of the laser pulse due to dispersion, as shown in figure 5.12b for GDD values of 0 fs^2 and 300 fs^2 . The figure shows the transversal charge distribution for both cases and the electric field of the laser in polarization direction. For 300 fs^2 the laser overlaps with the electron bunch, exerting a transversal force on the electrons, thereby inducing a wiggling motion in the polarization direction. This results in an increase in divergence.

(a) Interpolation of σ_θ dependency on GDD and z_{foc} . (b) Spatial charge distribution of the electron bunch for GDD = 0 fs^2 on top and GDD = 300 fs^2 on the bottom.

Figure 5.12: Impact of GDD on divergence.

5.2.3 Discussion of the model limits

The investigation of the individual beam parameters enables to describe the complex structure of the $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$ behavior in figure 5.2. It can be explained as a superposition of multiple effects. To reach high values for $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$, a low energy spread as well as a high total charge is necessary. A low energy spread E_{spread} occurs for higher absolute values of GDD. In contrast, the total charge Q_{total} decreases for higher GDD values. So the highest values for $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$ are reached as long as E_{spread} is reasonable small and the injected charge did not decrease significantly yet. To an extent, these two effects cancel each other out and create a stable GDD range between -200 fs^2 and 200 fs^2 . In this range, the electron beam is quite stable, but outside this area, $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$ changes rapidly, and the beam gets more unstable. The focus position mainly effects the peak position E_{peak} and the energy spread E_{spread} . For z_{foc} around 1.2 mm the spread is the smallest. $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$ slowly decreases for values deviating from this optimum.

It is important to note, that the identified dependencies, can only be taken as qualitative findings. It is extremely difficult if not impossible to make quantitative predictions, since not all parameters can be matched to the experiments. But it could be confirmed, that adapting the GDD has, in fact, an impact on stability of beam parameters, in particular $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$, as observed in experiments. This becomes obvious through the low slope of the polynomial interpolation for values close to 0 fs^2 and continually rising slope towards higher absolute values of GDD.

Also, the quality of the interpolation needs to be discussed. Polynomial interpolation only provides a model of reality and does not necessarily reflect it. The quality of the interpolation highly depends, next to the chosen interpolation nodes and the polynomial degree, on the function which is supposed to be modeled. The interpolated electron beam parameters have very different

dependencies on the parameter space and are a good example of the effect that the function to be interpolated has on the quality of the interpolation. For instance the interpolation of $(dQ/dE)_{\max}$ in figure 5.2 showed some oscillations towards very high and low values of $(dQ/dE)_{\max}$. To get an idea of how far these oscillations are from reality, the laser parameters corresponding to the maximum and minimum peak heights were determined and simulations were carried out. The maximum and minimum of the peak height are visualized in 5.2 and are located at $GDD = 220.3 \text{ fs}^2$ and $z_{\text{foc}} = 1.42 \text{ mm}$ or $GDD = -247.4 \text{ fs}^2$ and $z_{\text{foc}} = 1.80 \text{ mm}$ respectively. For these two points in the parameter space the electron beam quantities were calculated and compared to the initial interpolation. For the peak height, this can be seen in figure 5.13a, where the red circle in the upper plot corresponds to the maximum of the peak height and in the lower plot to the minimum. The deviation of the actual value, in the red circle, to the interpolation is clearly visible. For the maximum, the interpolation predicts a peak height value of 10.0 pC MeV^{-1} , but the value obtained by the simulation is only 8.0 pC MeV^{-1} . Which is a relative uncertainty of 25 %. Even worst is the prediction of the minimum, which was predicted with a peak height of 3.6 pC MeV^{-1} , but simulation suggested a value of 6.2 pC MeV^{-1} for this laser beam parameters, which corresponds to a relative uncertainty of 42 %.

The issue with this interpolation in particular is, that most of the peak height values are on a very constant level. The six central evaluated parameter points in the range of GDD between -150 fs^2 to 150 fs^2 and z_{foc} between 1.2 mm to 1.55 mm only vary between 7.92 pC MeV^{-1} and 8.87 pC MeV^{-1} , while the minimum of the whole parameter space lies at 4.66 pC MeV^{-1} . So there is a plateau in the middle of the parameter space. Such constant areas are very hard to describe with polynomials. This behavior leads to the described oscillations of the interpolation.

A different picture emerges for interpolations that do not feature such a plateau, such as the interpolation of the energy spread in figure 5.3. The energy spread of the two simulations, corresponding to the maximum and minimum of the peak height interpolation, were also determined and visualized as a red framed circle in figure 5.13b. In this case the predicted value by interpolation and the value determined by simulation are very close. The relative uncertainty is only 4.8 % for the maximum case or 3.0 % for the minimum case. Of course, the parameters are not chosen as the maximum or minimum of the E_{spread} interpolation and are not correlated to any oscillations of polynomial interpolation and one would expect smaller uncertainties than for the peak height. But as one can see in figure 5.3, in the case of the interpolation of the energy spread of the electron bunch no such oscillations are present. Also, this good prediction of the interpolation shows the potential of creating a model with multivariate interpolation. The situation is similar for E_{peak} , where the relative uncertainties lie at 4.0 % for the maximum case or 0.7 % for the minimum case. This can be seen in figure 5.13c.

 (a) $(dQ/dE)_{\max}$.

 (b) E_{spread} .

 (c) E_{peak} .

Figure 5.13: Evaluation of the quality of the multivariate interpolation. For the interpolation of $(dQ/dE)_{\max}$ the parameters for the maximum and minimum where evaluated, see figure 5.2, and simulations for these parameters were performed. The results are shown as the red framed circles, where the maximum of $(dQ/dE)_{\max}$ corresponds to the upper plots and the minimum to the lower plots. The colormap in the background is an excerpt of the interpolation of the single electron beam parameters in figure 5.2 for 5.13a, 5.3 for 5.13b and 5.8 for 5.13c.

5.3 Investigation of plasma density shape and beam waist dependencies

5.3.1 Parameters

For the second parameter scan, parameters were selected for which it was observed in the experiment that the parameters had to be set dependent on each other. In experiments, the signature in the synthetic spectrometer could be significantly improved by changing the distance between the exit of the gas nozzle and the laser axis. In general, the density profile is not variable, but the distance between the exit of the gas nozzle and the laser axis modifies the shape of the up and down ramp of the density profile and can be varied relatively easily by moving the nozzle. It was recently observed at HZDR that changing this distance can benefit the peak charge. In addition, the beam waist w_0 seems to have an effect on the electron bunch, which can hardly be investigated in detail in experiments. To gain a deeper understanding of these dependencies the shape of the plasma density profile and the beam waist were selected for a second parameter scan.

Variation of the slope of the up and down ramps of the plasma profile

Figure 5.14: Definition of the up and down ramp slope of the plasma density profile.

By decreasing the distance between the laser axis and the nozzle, the up ramp and down ramp of the plasma density become steeper. The plasma density profile consists of 4 parts, the up ramp, the plateau, the down ramp, and the background plasma. The up and down ramp are modeled by a Gaussian function given in equation 5.11. The parameter that is varied to represent the different shooting heights is the standard deviation σ of equation 5.11, μ corresponds to the position of the beginning or end of the plateau.

$$n_e(z) = n_{\text{base}} \cdot e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z-\mu}{\sigma} \right)^2} \quad (5.11)$$

The overall length of the profile should remain constant at approximately 3.5 mm. Therefore, the beginning of the plateau is always chosen at $3 \cdot \sigma + 0.3$ mm, the latter being a constant offset to make the start of the profile smoother. The end of the plateau is defined at $3.5 \text{ mm} - 3 \cdot \sigma + 0.3$ mm. After the down ramp, background plasma with a constant density of $3.8 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-3}$ is added. The resulting density profile is shown in figure 5.14, where the plasma density over the simulation length of 5 mm is depicted. The original slope, which was also used for the optimization run, was $\sigma = 0.3$ mm. The range for the slope was chosen to be between 0.25 mm to 0.35 mm. In reality

the integrated charge density on the course of propagating through the plasma, has to remain constant for different shooting heights. This is not fulfilled with the defined plasma profile. To fulfill this, the length of the plasma profile would have been adapted to the slope. This would have an impact of the laser propagation and would require adaptations of the focus position and total propagation length. Simplifying by not having a constant integrated density was chosen to consider only the slope.

Variation of beam waist

The beam waist was varied between 17 μm to 23 μm , keeping the found optimum of 20 μm in the center. The values are given as the distance from the laser axis at focus position where the intensity is decreased by a factor of $1/e^2$. Investigating this parameter is of particular interest for experimental recommendations, since this parameter can only be varied through time-consuming or expensive adjustments to the beamline, such as using a different focusing parabolic mirror or by inserting a mask into the laser beam path. In addition, when the beam waist is adjusted with a mask, several other laser properties change, such as the Rayleigh length, the transverse mode structure, and the beam energy. Therefore, the isolated effect of the beam waist is difficult to investigate experimentally. Knowledge gained from simulations is therefore necessary to investigate the effect and sensitivity of the electron beam on the beam waist.

5.3.2 Dependencies

To get a first impression on the impact of the parameters, an overview is showcased in figure 5.15. It shows the electron bunch in the synthetic spectrometer for three different density slopes between 0.25 mm to 0.35 mm and for three different beam waists between 17.4 μm to 20 μm . The highest values for the peak charge $(dQ/dE)_{\text{max}}$ as well as the lowest energy spread are reached in the simulations, where the density slope is adjusted to the beam waist. This can be seen on the diagonal from the lower left corner to the upper right corner, or from steep density slopes and small beam waist to shallower density slopes and larger beam waist in the figure 5.15. The occurrence of these good beam properties on a diagonal in the parameter spaces implies that both parameters must be adjusted to each other in order to obtain a good beam quality with a high peak height $(dQ/dE)_{\text{max}}$. Since the exact plasma density profile is not known, it is not possible to give recommendations about the exact values or the position of this ideal diagonal in the parameter space. But with the result, it is reasonable to give recommendations in which direction to adapt the parameters in order to maximize $(dQ/dE)_{\text{max}}$. To be able to do this, it is necessary to distinguish if a given charge distribution $d^2Q/dEd\theta$ is positioned in the upper left corner of figure 5.15 or in the lower right corner and therefore in which direction which parameter needs to be changed to obtain good electron beam properties. To quantify this, one needs to find parameters or features of the electron bunch that differentiate this two cases.

An examination of 5.15 reveals that the lower right corner exhibits a considerably lower total charge than the upper part. Additionally, the energy spread appears to increase in the upper left corner. A more detailed analysis of these two properties was performed. Therefore, a simulation was performed and evaluated for each interpolation node. The evaluated beam properties were interpolated with a sixth-degree polynomial using MinterPy.

Total beam charge Q_{total}

The interpolation result for the total beam charge is illustrated in Figure 5.16. The charge is highest in the upper left corner, corresponding to larger beam waists and flatter slopes and lowest for

Figure 5.15: Overview over electron bunch dependencies on plasma density slope and beam waist. For three different values of the beam waist and the slope the synthetic spectrometer is depicted.

small beam waists and steeper slopes. However, the impact of the slope on the charge is relatively minor compared to the impact of the beam waist.

A possible explanation for the charge dependence on the beam waist is that as the beam waist decreases, the total energy of the laser beam decreases, because the intensity represented by the dimensionless field strength parameter a_0 has remained constant for all simulations. With a lower laser beam energy, the plasma propagation is different and the duration during which trapping can occur may be shorter. The intensity represented by the dimensionless field strength parameter a_0 has remained constant for all simulations. An equal intensity, but a smaller beam waist, results in a decrease of total laser beam energy. To investigate the impact of the injection mechanism and not the beam energy, the laser intensity was adapted so that the total laser energy becomes equal for different beam waists. To adapt a simulation i with beam waist $w_{0,i}$, to have the same laser energy as a simulation j with $a_{0,j}$ and $w_{0,j}$, one employs that the energy is proportional the squared electric field of the laser. This can be described in terms of a_0 and w_0 , as in equation 2.2 and results in:

$$E \propto |\vec{E}|^2 = \left(\frac{a_0 m_e c w_0}{q_e} \right)^2 \Rightarrow a_{0,i} = \frac{a_{0,j} w_{0,j}}{w_{0,i}} \quad (5.12)$$

In order to facilitate the comparison, the laser intensities for all simulations presented figure 5.15 have been adjusted to align with the energy of a laser with $w_{0,j} = 20 \mu\text{m}$ and $a_{0,j} = 2.3127$. This corresponds to the simulations in the first row of figure 5.15. The electron spectrometer output of these energy adapted simulations are shown in figure 5.17.

The overall shape of the electron beam in the electron spectrometer remains constant, independently of the laser intensity a_0 and the associated constant total laser beam energy, where overall shape refers specifically to energy spread, divergence and occurrence of the high-energy tail. What changes is the peak position E_{peak} . This shifts for lower w_0 , or higher a_0 respectively,

Figure 5.16: Total charge Q_{total} dependency on the plasma density slope and laser beam waist w_0 .

towards higher energies. A possible explanation could be, that for higher a_0 a slightly stronger wake is driven, which would result in a stronger accelerating field, which would result in a higher energy of the electrons.

The impact on the charge is shown in figure 5.18. The total electron beam charge varies for the initial simulations between 380 pC and 578 pC and for the adapted laser energy only between 481 pC and 587 pC, reducing the variation of charge from 198 pC to 106 pC. In the adapted case the charge variation is now more prominent for the variation of the density slope and not for the beam waist anymore. This supports the hypothesis that the charge dependence on the beam waist results from the different laser intensities and the resulting different trapping durations. This means, that the energy spectra in figure 5.18 all have a comparable total charge, so total charge is not a good candidate for distinguishing which direction to change the beam waist to get higher values of $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$.

Energy spread E_{spread}

The spread is another electron beam parameter, which might indicate in which regime the acceleration process operates. The interpolation of the single E_{spread} values is shown in figure 5.19. As discussed in 5.2.3 oscillations of the polynomial interpolation can occur for certain functions. The interpolation in figure 5.19 shows features of such oscillations, like the valley in the central upper part of the plot, where the interpolation predicts much lower values for E_{spread} than have been simulated in this section. Therefore, the interpolations should be interpreted with some caution.

Nevertheless, the lowest values of E_{spread} are located in the dark blue area in the lower half of figure 5.19. This is also where the highest values of peak height $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\text{max}}$ occur, and the previously described diagonal of good electron beam properties correlates with the dark blue area of low energy spread.

With the overview picture of the parameter space 5.15 it was suspected, that the energy spread increases in the upper left corner of the parameter space, corresponding to bigger beam waists and a steeper slope of the density ramp. In the analysis in figure 5.19 this cannot be confirmed. The slope increases towards the upper left corner as well as towards the lower right corner.

Figure 5.17: Overview over electron bunch dependencies on plasma density slope and beam waist. In comparison to figure 5.15 the total beam energy for each simulation is equal. This is achieved by adapting the laser intensity according to equation 5.12, resulting in higher values for a_0 for lower values of w_0 .

Figure 5.18: Impact on total electron beam charge between of beam waist and density slope with and without constant total laser energy. On the left side the total charge of the initial simulations in figure 5.15 and on the right the simulations with adapted laser beam energy of figure 5.17 is shown. The visualization of the charge is through a nearest neighbor interpolation.

But the behavior still differs between these two cases, which is visualized in figure 5.20. In the upper left corner the spread increases towards higher energies, as can be seen in green in figure 5.20. There the high energy tail occurs, as already discussed in 5.2.2. For the lower right corner, corresponding to smaller beam waist and steeper slope of the plasma ramps, the energy spread increases towards lower energies, as shown in orange in figure 5.20. For simulations with a low charge and low peak height, this leads to very low values for the lower energy limit, where the

Figure 5.19: E_{spread} dependency on the plasma density shape and w_0 .

lower energy limit defines the lower bound for the calculation of the energy spread. In these cases this lower energy limit lies at values far below the peak energy.

Figure 5.20: Comparison of the energy histograms for different density slopes and beam waists. The filled area corresponds to the range, which is considered for the determination energy spread.

To conclude, energy spread as defined here does not differ much between the case of larger beam waist and a steeper slope of the density ramp and the case of smaller beam waist and shallower slope. However, the energy distribution differs between these two cases, as can be seen in figure 5.20.

Peak height $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\max}$

How rapidly the electron beam parameters are changing can also be seen by investigating the $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\max}$ parameter. The peak height is pretty constant for the majority of the chosen parameters, as one can see in figure 5.21. There the dependency of the peak height on the plasma density slope and the beam waist is shown, once using the polynomial interpolation on the left side and on the right side using a linear interpolation. The polynomial interpolation in figure 5.21a shows very high oscillations, because polynomial interpolation, as discussed in 5.2.3, is not suitable to represent plateaus. The linear interpolation in figure 5.21b grants a good intuition about the parameter space. In the lower right corner the peak height decreases drastically. The highest, and therefore best values, are reached close to this drastic decrease.

Both of the interpolations shown in figure 5.21 lack an accurate description of where the peak height values begin to decrease and where the global peak heights are greatest. To describe such abrupt changes of the slope, a finer sampling close to this region would be necessary, independently of the interpolation method.

In this simulation study, a sufficient level of understanding of the parameter space was achieved. It can be said that for stable beam parameters, the beam waist should be adapted to the distance between the laser axis and the gas nozzle in such a way that a relatively high value of $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\max}$ is achieved, but possibly the high energy tail occurs. Operating the LPA at the highest possible peak height can result in a very unstable electron beam parameters.

Figure 5.21: Comparison of different interpolation methods for the $(\frac{dQ}{dE})_{\max}$ dependency on the beam waist w_0 and the plasma density slope.

5.3.3 Discussion

The electron beam dependencies on the plasma density shape and the beam waist were investigated in a qualitative manner. It was confirmed that the electron beam properties depend on both investigated parameters, and therefore it is necessary to adapt the beam waist to the shape of the density profile or the distance between the gas nozzle and the laser axis, respectively, in order to obtain good electron beam properties. The electron beam parameters were found to be comparably stable for higher beam waist values and a flatter density slope. The beam quality, meaning the charge density per energy and divergence, decreases rapidly once a certain threshold for the slope and beam waist is reached. A similar dependence has already been observed in

experiments at the HZDR, where the electron spectrometer measurement was compared for different distances between the nozzle exit and the laser axis.

Since the beam waist in experiments is altered by inserting a mask between the laser and the plasma, additional transversal modifications of the laser envelope occur. This has, as shown in section 4.3.2, a significant impact on the electron beam properties. The potential transversal modification of the laser beam were not considered here, because the exact alteration of the shape are not determined in experiments yet and are therefore unknown so far. Further uncertainties are induced to the unknown exact impact of the laser shooting height on the plasma density.

The polynomial interpolation turned out to be more difficult than for the first parameter space in section 5.2. This is visible, for example, in the interpolation in figure 5.21a. The interpolation seems to fail with steep slope on one side of the diagonal and the very shallow slope on the other side. For this steep slope for w_0 between $17.0\ \mu\text{m}$ to $18.0\ \mu\text{m}$ the parameter space is too loosely sampled and therefore not enough information exists in order to provide an accurate representation of the behavior in this area. Even for other interpolation methods like linear interpolation (in figure 5.21b) only coarse assumptions about this area can be drawn. Nevertheless, the interpolation methods were a good tool to quickly get a rough understanding of the underlying dependencies and provide input on what features might be interesting to investigate in the future.

5.4 Potential of interpolation - overview and outlook of parameter scans

With the help of the interpolation, multiple interesting dependencies were discovered that potentially allow for better beam control.

The parameter space spanning GDD and focus position is of interest because it is known in experiments that GDD has an impact on the stability and quality of the electron beam parameters. The found dependencies of the electron beam properties on the group delay dispersion and the focus position are summarized as follows: As expected it is advantageous to have relatively small values of GDD in order to accelerate an electron beam with low divergence and high charge. Electron beam properties such as energy spread and total beam charge depend on both GDD and z_{foc} values, while the peak energy E_{peak} can be varied with the focus position almost independently of GDD. In addition, with the simulations of the GDD - z_{foc} parameter space, investigations could be carried out that allow explaining the occurrence of the energy spread.

In the second parameter space examined, considering the plasma density slope and the beam waist, both parameters significantly influence the electron beam properties. Achieving optimal electron beam characteristics requires adaptation of these parameters to one another. This is especially important for obtaining good values of the peak height $(dQ/dE)_{\text{max}}$. For a small beam waist and shallow slope of the plasma density, the beam quality in terms of total charge and peak height decreases drastically at one point. Before reaching that steep descent, the highest beam quality is obtained. As the beam waist increases and the plasma density slope becomes steeper, the electron beam properties become more stable. According to the simulations conducted in this study, transitioning from the regime of poor electron beam properties to a more stable regime could be achieved by increasing the distance between the gas nozzle exit and the laser axis or the laser beam waist. Since the distance between the nozzle exit and the laser exit can be varied relatively easily by moving the gas nozzle, these dependencies are under investigation and already show comparable results to those presented here.

Multivariate polynomial interpolations can provide good models of dependencies that can be represented by polynomials within the bounds of the parameter space, such as the energy spread and the peak energy dependence on the GDD and focus position, as has been shown

in figure 5.13. Such precise predictions are not feasible with linear interpolation. It is also a great tool for visualizing these dependencies in a comprehensive way. Since any function can be approximated by a polynomial, as discussed in section 5.1.1, polynomial interpolation should be able to represent any function in a sufficient way, but choosing the right polynomial degree and the right interpolation points is not trivial and adds complexity to the process. If the choice of these things is not appropriate for the parameter dependencies to be modeled, the interpolation can be very different from the realistic target function. Then oscillations can occur. This is in particular likely in regions where the function values that the interpolation should model form a plateau, or have a steep edge. If one has an assumption on how the parameter space behaves one should choose the degree of the polynomial accordingly. Another possibility would be to carry out the interpolation in numerous smaller areas, or in other words adapt the polynomial degree to the behavior of the target function. In parameter spaces that are difficult to describe with a single polynomial, such as plateaus, which require a lower polynomial degree, and edges, which require a higher polynomial degree, these regions could be considered separately.

In conclusion, the presented method provides a map from the parameter space to the electron beam parameters and allow recommendations for experiments. Polynomial interpolation can be a good choice for functions that can be represented by a polynomial, but the results should always be checked for reliability. Then, multivariate interpolation can be a great tool for evaluation and visualization.

6 Conclusion and Outlook

Overall, this thesis presented a systematic approach to investigate the dependencies of electron witness beams in laser plasma accelerators on different laser pulses and densities. Several methods and tools such as workflow engines, Bayesian optimization and multivariate interpolation were used.

The workflow engine Snakemake was established in PICongGPU, which allows simple execution of various PICongGPU applications. Due to the generality of the implementation, the workflow engine can and has already been used for projects outside of this thesis, such as other parameter scans or data generation for machine learning applications. A further, continuous development and improvement of the workflow in accordance with the requirements of PICongGPU users will be pursued. For this thesis, this workflow engine simplified and accelerated the consecutive studies of the sensitivity of laser wakefield accelerators utilizing self-truncated ionization injection.

The approach of reproducing an experimental electron spectrum with the help of the Bayesian optimization algorithm showed promising results. It was possible to match the energy and divergence of simulations with the experimentally obtained values over the course of less than 30 simulation. During the process of reconstructing experimental results, important insights about the present experimental setup were found. The most important example of this is the background plasma. Only with this better understanding of the relevance of the background plasma it was possible to reproduce the low divergence achieved in the experiment in LWFA simulations. The existence of this background plasma was later validated by the experimental team. The reproduction of realistic electron beams with low divergence has been a challenge for simulations, often blamed on numerical instabilities. Now, with the background plasma, an essential process has been found that has a greater impact on the divergence than numerics and helped to overcome this problem.

It was also shown that numerical effects have a significant effect on the electron beam properties. Due to the highly detailed study of the electron properties, non-physical radiation effects of unexpected intensity were found for different field solvers. This finding, led to further investigations of their numerical origin outside the work of this thesis. These investigations concern the necessary setup, especially the grid resolution, for the solver to run numerically stable and should lead to a more trustworthy configuration in the future.

The found optimal setup represents the experimental electron beam parameters in a remarkable way, but in the end one can never fully know to what extent the found parameters correspond to the experimental settings. The optimization algorithm could at least quickly indicate if the chosen parameter space contains a setting that is suitable to reproduce the experimental electron beam results. An advantage of using Gaussian processes as a surrogate for Bayesian optimization

is that a Gaussian process can account for an uncertainty of each data point when creating the surrogate function. This opens up many more applications and allows Bayesian optimization to be used in experiments. In the future, it may be possible to build a surrogate model from simulated and experimental data. Then, experiments and simulations could benefit from each other and learn automatically. This requires a better understanding of the uncertainties of each parameter and measurement, and of the differences between the physical setups of experiments and simulations. The findings about the required simulation setup in this thesis have been another step to improve this understanding.

With the found simulation setup, a sensitivity and dependence on 4 different laser and plasma parameters was investigated using multivariate interpolation. The interpolation proved to be a helpful but also challenging tool. The dependence of the quality of the interpolation on the parameter space to be interpolated makes it difficult to use for unknown parameter dependencies. For parameter spaces where a rough understanding is already achieved, it can be a great tool to create a model of the existing dependencies.

Despite the limitations of the method, several dependencies and correlations between the investigated laser and plasma parameters and the electron beam properties were found. The most prominent were the reason for the occurrence of the high energy tail and the impact the group-delay-dispersion has on it as well as the non-monotonous dependency of the focus position and the peak energy. These findings are potentially beneficial for experimentalists for tuning the electron beam properties.

For the second parameter space, where the beam waist and the slope of the plasma density profile were varied, a correlated dependency of the electron beam properties was found. In experiments, the distance between the exit of the gas nozzle and the axis of the laser beam, which affects the slope of the plasma density gradient, can be varied by moving the gas nozzle closer to the laser beam axis. The correlation between beam waist and density gradient allows for a simpler optimization: instead of adjusting the laser beam waist one can equivalently adjust the nozzle height to achieve the same effect.

For most of this parameter space, the beam properties are stable, especially the peak height. However, when the slope of the plasma ramps becomes too shallow, the peak height changes abruptly and the beam properties are generally worse. These results will hopefully make it easier for the experimentalist to tune the LPA setup into a stable regime. Similar dependencies have been observed in experiments, confirming the quality of the simulations performed.

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List of Abbreviations

AOFDTD	arbitrary order finite-difference time domain
CKC	Cole-Karkkainen-Cowan
CSV	comma-separated values
CTR	cathode-ray tube
DAG	directed acyclic graph
DRACO	Dresden laser acceleration source
FEL	free electron laser
FWHM	full width at half maximum
GDD	group-delay-dispersion
HPC	high-performance computing
HZDR	Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf e. V.
LCB	lower confidence bound
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
LHS	latin hypercube sampling
LPA	Laser particle accelerator
LWFA	Laser wakefield accelerator
PIC	Particle in cell
PIConGPU	particle-in-cell on GPU
STII	self-truncated ionization injection
tbg	template batch generator
TOD	third-order dispersion

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Erklärung

Ich versichere, dass ich die vorliegende Abschlussarbeit selbständig verfasst und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt habe. Ich reiche sie erstmals als Prüfungsleistung ein. Mir ist bekannt, dass eine Täuschung mit der Note "nicht ausreichend" (5,0) geahndet wird.

I hereby declare that I have written this final thesis independently and have listed all used sources and aids. I am submitting this thesis for the first time as a piece of assessed academic work. I understand that attempted deceit will result in the failing grade "not sufficient" (5.0).

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